

Deliverable Report D2.1

Compendium of models

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¹R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Acronyms Listed in this Document	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
API	Application Programming Interface
CSS	Chemical Strategy for Sustainability
EC	European Commission
ENV	Environment
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HH	Human Health
IOP	Impact Outcome Pathway
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
PBPK	Physiologically based pharmacokinetic models
PoD	Point of Departure
QSAR	Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship
QSPR	Quantitative Structure Property Relationship
s-LCA	Social LCA
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
STOT - RE	Specific Target Organ Toxicity – Repeated Exposure
STOT - SE	Specific Target Organ Toxicity – Single Exposure
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The current deliverable (D2.1) provides a description of the development of the INSIGHT compendium of models and tools (platforms, software, toolboxes) that will serve as the basis of the INSIGHT modeling framework. An identification and collection strategy has been followed to gather the relevant tools that will eventually form the INSIGHT model graph. The tools are differentiated into internal and external tools, where the former are tools developed by INSIGHT partners and the latter are derived from external sources. Priority has been given to internal tools to facilitate seamless computational integration and ensure direct accessibility and maximum interoperability. Analysis of the internal tools identified several gaps in terms of their coverage of the safety and sustainability space, which will be effectively covered through the integration of external tools. Overall, 93 tools have been collected, including 16 environmental fate models, 27 exposure models (environmental, occupational and consumer), 20 physiologically based pharmacokinetics (PBPK) models, 27 quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models, 11 bioinformatics tools, 17 models for hazard prediction based on New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) or *in vitro*, 2 life cycle assessment (LCA) software packages, 1 software for social LCA (s-LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC) and 5 models for characterizing toxicity impacts in LCA.

In terms of describing the identified tools, a detailed definition of their objectives, implementation (availability of an application programming interface (API), a graphical user interface (GUI) or Docker containers, and their locations), and main functionalities is provided. Moreover, three types of mapping have been performed: 1) mapping of modeling requirements, 2) mapping of impacts covered by the tools and 3) mapping of the SSbD indicators covered by the tool. Another element addressed in this document is the FAIRness status evaluation of the INSIGHT internal tools. For this evaluation, a dedicated evaluation form including 26 questions pertinent to the FAIR principles as applied to research software was circulated to tool providers. The primary goal of this activity was to gather an initial overview of the current status of the tools' FAIRness level and to identify hotspots for improvement.

The results of this analysis revealed several gaps related to modeling requirements, impact assessment and the corresponding Safe and Sustainable by design (SSbD) indicators. At the level of internal tools, gaps have been identified in occupational exposure modeling and in the availability of socioeconomic assessment models. Moreover, both the internal and external tools address impacts on human health and the environment, while there is one external tool that covers socioeconomic impacts. Thus, focus is being directed towards the implementation of tools that cover socioeconomic impacts. Finally, the gap analysis highlights the importance of integrating models that address the entire range of environmental impact indicators. Future actions will include establishing detailed and harmonized descriptions of the input-output relationships of the tools, continuously improving their FAIRness and aligning them with the modeling needs of the INSIGHT case studies.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Description of Task 2.1

INSIGHT WP2 is dedicated to the development of the INSIGHT model graph and model implementation. Within WP2, Task 2.1 collects the publicly available models for integration. The main goal of Task 2.1 is to provide a variety of models that address the scope of the INSIGHT model graph. These models will address the safety and sustainability aspects of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, covering the four levels of impact (health, environmental, social and economic). In detail, the INSIGHT model compendium will include models for safety assessment, such as environmental fate, exposure, Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) and Physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models, and models for sustainability assessment, such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) models and models for socioeconomic analysis. In this document, the identification and collection strategy for relevant models, as well as tools that incorporate models, their specifications (e.g., links to code, to the download page or to the log in page, availability of an Application Programming Interface (API), Graphical User Interface (GUI), programming language), functionalities (inputs, outputs, covered impacts) and FAIRness status are presented. The models collected in Task 2.1 will be implemented in the other tasks of INSIGHT and will be used to structure the model graph database.

1.2 Safe and Sustainable by Design

The European Union (EU) has underscored the need for a toxic-free and climate-neutral environment through the European Green Deal (EC, 2019). In this context, the European Commission (EC) has delivered a set of action plans, including the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) (EC, 2020) and the Zero Pollution Action Plan (EC, 2021), reflecting the transition towards a SSbD approach. SSbD aims to enhance the design and development of chemicals and materials, with a focus on minimizing health, environmental and social impacts along the entire life cycle. It is a holistic, voluntary and pre-market approach, that aims to integrate safety and sustainability considerations as early as possible in the design-development process, considering the entire life cycle of a chemical or material. SSbD is considered to be a prevention strategy, that aims to foster innovation by enhancing the safety and sustainability characteristics of a chemical or material and prevent harms from arising later.

In 2022, the EC Joint Research Center (JRC) introduced a framework for SSbD (Caldeira et al., 2022a; Caldeira et al., 2022b), which comprises two parts: the (re)design and assessment part, respectively. In the (re)design phase, specific SSbD principles are followed to guide the design process of a chemical or material and structure an SSbD assessment. The assessment part, is a comprehensive five-step approach for the safety and sustainability assessment of a new or existing chemical or material, as described below:

- Step 1: Hazard Assessment;
- Step 2: Human health and safety aspects during the production and processing phases;
- Step 3: Human health and environmental aspects in the final application phase;
- Step 4: Environmental Sustainability assessment;
- Step 5: Socioeconomic analysis.

Steps 1-3 refer to safety assessment including hazard, occupational exposure, environmental exposure, and consumer exposure assessment. On the other hand, steps 4-5 are related to the sustainability assessment including environmental and socioeconomic aspects, where the 5th step is considered optional. The SSbD framework is considered an iterative process, that incorporates safety and sustainability considerations at each iteration, depending on the data availability and level of detail across the innovation process (Abbate et al., 2024). Within INSIGHT, the SSbD framework will be

integrated by developing a mechanistic impact assessment framework that aligns with the SSbD principles, as detailed below.

1.2.1 INSIGHT SSbD Framework

INSIGHT aims to implement the current SSbD framework, by incorporating the mechanistic evaluation of the chemical impact based on integrated and mechanistic impact assessment. INSIGHT will expand the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework to accommodate mechanistic considerations for impact assessment, by developing an integrated framework based on the novel concept of Impact Outcome Pathways (IOP). IOPs will be developed for each safety and sustainability area of concern (health, environment, society, economics) within the SSbD framework. The IOPs will support the development of an integrated SSbD framework including regulatory decision rules and visualization, and can facilitate organization of existing knowledge, identification of knowledge gaps, development of quantitative models, and systematic design of impact assessment strategies.

Figure 1: The INSIGHT framework for integrated impact assessment and SSbD

The integrated impact assessment and IOP framework developed within the project will be mapped to the tiered EU SSbD principles and framework. The multi-layer framework of INSIGHT for chemicals and materials SSbD, consists of a data graph (WP3), a model graph (WP2) and an IOP graph (WP4) that together enable the prediction of the health, environmental, social and economic impacts of chemicals and materials (Figure 1). The three graphs will be systematically interlinked and used for integrated impact assessment of chemicals and materials for next generation integrated SSbD.

1.2.2 INSIGHT model graph

The compendium of models/tools structured within T2.1 will form the basis of the INSIGHT model graph. In the INSIGHT model graph, the tools/models are the nodes, which are interconnected to each other by data input/output as well as prediction endpoint characteristics. The models will use state-of-the-art approaches, including consensus strategies and multi-view models³. Consensus strategies, such as “mixture of experts” or ensemble methods will be developed to combine multiple models. A range of safety and sustainability models for risk assessment will be developed. Moreover, interoperability with the modeling efforts of the European Partnership for Assessment of the Risks of Chemical (PARC⁴) will be ensured (due to overlap of partners and ongoing efforts to collaborate with PARC initiated via the PARC SynNet process- see Deliverable D5.1 for details) and a graph model database will be created. Multi-view models will be built taking into consideration the various data representations for chemicals and materials available in the data knowledge graph (WP3). Statistical modeling and advanced machine learning methods will be applied to develop QSAR models for sustainability assessment and to reduce uncertainty in risk assessments. In addition, the expertise of INSIGHT partners in toxicogenomics and PBPK modeling will be leveraged to expand the applicability of the INSIGHT framework. The ultimate goal is to create more accurate and reliable models while providing transparent information on how predictions are made, leading to better decision-making. The model graph will be interconnected with the data graph (WP3), which is designed to be a graph database management system for social, economic, health and environmental impact assessment of chemicals and materials. Based on the model/data needs for impact assessment, specific computational pipelines will be developed within WP4. Finally, the INSIGHT model inventory will guide the development of new models by identifying current modeling gaps and needs for assessing chemical and materials impacts. A knowledge graph will be used to develop layered networks containing individual data points (WP3) and models (WP2) designed to respond to a specific question and to model a specific endpoint throughout the life of a chemical/material. The output of multiple models will be used to define impact-informative key events (KEs) and expand the AOP framework to define novel mechanistic models of IOPs. The individual impacts will be combined into a novel holistic evaluation of the overall impact (integrated impact) through multiple computational strategies.

³ Jordan & Jacobs, 1994, Friedman, & Popescu, 2008, Lin et al., 2010

⁴ <https://www.eu-parc.eu/>

2 COMPENDIUM OF MODELS

2.1 Identification and collection model strategy

To compile and structure the INSIGHT compendium of models, an identification and collection model strategy was followed (Figure 2). The identification of models was based on several criteria, including the impacts that need to be covered (health, environmental, social, economic), the model availability from the INSIGHT partners or externally and the alignment with PARC’s modeling efforts. PARC has a dedicated activity on the development of the PARC SSbD toolbox (Sarigiannis et al., 2024). The PARC SSbD toolbox will provide all the relevant tools, methods and data for the operationalization of the SSbD framework. Therefore, the alignment and interoperability of the INSIGHT model graph with the PARC toolbox is of high importance.

Figure 2: Model collection strategy

The first step of the model collection strategy was to identify models/tools developed by internal partners, which included around 93 models and tools (Table 1). The identification and inclusion of internal models/tools are particularly important in the construction of the INSIGHT compendium of models and model graph, as they enable more prompt and flexible integration into the INSIGHT framework. Furthermore, one critical factor that drives the model/tool selection is the availability of their source code, ensuring transparency and adaptability, and facilitating interoperability. Therefore, prioritizing the list of internal models/tools not only facilitates their integration but also allows for their direct accessibility and proper adaptability to fulfill the respective modeling requirements of the INSIGHT framework. Along with the code availability, another essential criterion during the model/tool selection process was the availability of an API or Docker container. These aspects provide the flexibility to integrate tools independent of their implementation and hosting location, while ensuring smooth deployment and interaction with the other components of the framework. Based on the information regarding the characteristics of the internal models/tools (This section outlines the

important characteristics necessary for the implementation of tools within the INSIGHT modeling framework. The implementation of the tools requires the availability or integration of an API, a docker for deploying models, a GUI, and the specification of the type of application or the programming language employed in their development. In terms of implementation, 36 (30 internal and 6 external) of the tools provide an API and 83 (58 internal and 25 external) of them have a GUI available. Moreover, there is a variation in the application type and the programming language of the models. The criteria against which the models are assessed are presented in Table 3 (internal models and tools) and Table 4 (external models and tools) below.

Table 3 it is evident that not all tools are equipped with an API or Docker container. However, most of the models have one or other solution under development or it will be developed in the context of the project.

Moreover, the current list of models/tools is not definitive and will be further enhanced according to the modeling needs and gaps of the INSIGHT framework. Thus, another significant step of the model collection strategy is prioritizing the implementation of the models/tools covering, if not all, then most of the project's modeling requirements (Table 5). Some of the models/tools can cover the same modeling requirements ensuring some much-needed redundancy and/or providing a breadth of coverage of the chemicals and materials space. To prevent any unnecessary overlap and maximize the efficiency of our approach, specific functionalities of each model/tool will be targeted based on the framework needs, such as the implementation of case studies (WPI). This will also entail a careful consideration of the respective endpoints of each model/tool (Table 9).

The identification and collection of internal models/tools was followed by the collection of models/tools developed by external sources. The latter were identified by recommendations and insights from internal partners, who have expertise in relevant fields. Thus, partners suggested the most appropriate models/tools that meet the requirements of the SSbD framework. These requirements are related to the capacity of the models to furnish the indicators for both safety and sustainability suggested in the JRC framework (Caldeira et al., 2022a), based on the endpoints that the models predict. In order to provide a clear understanding of the indicators that are not addressed by the identified models, a mapping was established between the two (section 2.5). This procedure allowed for the identification of the missing indicators and the enhancement of the current models list. As mentioned above, a prioritization procedure will be followed in terms of model/tool implementation. Within this scope, and considering the identified modeling gaps, the list of external models/tools (

Table 4) will be leveraged to enhance the functionalities of the INSIGHT framework.

2.2 Inventory of tools

Overall, 93 tools have been collected, including 16 environmental fate models, 27 exposure models (environmental, occupational and consumer), 20 PBPK models, 27 QSAR models, 11 bioinformatic tools, 17 models for hazard prediction based on NAMs/*in vitro*, 2 LCA software package, 1 software for s-LCA and LCC and 5 models for characterizing toxicity impacts in LCA. The internal tools represent 71% (66 tools) of the inventory, while external sources account for the remaining 29% (27 tools). In the following tables (Table 1, Table 2) the internal and external tools are described respectively, including their main objective, location (e.g., link to available code, to the download page or to the log in page), the type of tool and the developer. Regarding their location, 12 of the models have an available code repository, while most can be found online to be used via a cloud platform or can be downloaded. It is imperative to highlight that the following inventory is diverse and comprises different types of tools, including models, software, platforms and methods.

Table 1: Inventory of internal (INSIGHT partner-developed) tools

Tool name		Objective	Location	Type of tool	Developer
Artificial intelligence / machine learning (AI/ML) based prediction of aquatic toxicity		AI/ML-based model (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) suited for prediction of aquatic toxicity (lethal concentration for 50% of organisms, LC50) of organic chemicals.	Under development (GitHub)	Model	RIVM jointly with ULEIDEN
AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity of metallic nanomaterials		AI/ML-based model suited for prediction of aquatic toxicity of metallic nanomaterials	-	Model	ULEIDEN
AOP Fingerprint		A tool for AOP-based chemical safety assessment	To be implemented	Method	TAU
BMDx		BMDx is a tool BMDx for easy benchmark dose (BMD) analysis on omics data across multiple time points and experiments	https://github.com/Greco-Lab/BMDx	Software	TAU
Enalos Cloud Platform		A web-based application that provides a suite of tools for predictive modeling and simulation in the fields of chemistry, nanotechnology, and materials science	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/all.html	Platform	NovaM
Enalos Cloud Platform	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability	Predicts blood-brain barrier permeability of molecules using deep learning	Enalos Cloud Platform	Model	NovaM
	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction	AI/ML-based model for the prediction of Caco-2 cell permeability to estimate oral drug permeability.	Enalos Cloud Platform	Model	NovaM
	ASCOT	Web tool for digital construction and energy minimization of Ag, CuO, TiO ₂ nanoparticles (NPs)	ASCOT Tool on Enalos Cloud	Web tool	NovaM
	Biokinetics Model	Prediction of nickel (Ni) release from cardiovascular devices to estimate exposure levels	Enalos Biokinetics Model	Model	NovaM
	Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition	Prediction of K562 cell growth inhibition, potentially aiding in drug discovery for β -thalassemia treatment	http://enalos.insilico.tox.com/K562/	Model	NovaM

Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs	Predicting cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles using computational descriptors	https://cellviability.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/2/	Model	NovaM
Ecotox	Predict acute toxicity of freshly dispersed and aged NMs to Daphnia magna	https://ecotox.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	Model	NovaM
Enalos InSilicoNano	Decision support tool for nanoparticle design and virtual screening	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/QNAR_PaCa2/		NovaM
Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Predict toxicity of Iron Oxide nanoparticles (NPs)	http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/QNAR_IronOxide_Toxicity/	Platform	NovaM
Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool	Predict zeta potential of nanomaterials (NMs) based on TEM images	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/ZetaPotential/	Model	NovaM
In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	Web-based tool for simulating engineered nanomaterial (ENM) fate and transport to derive dosimetry	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/riskgone/InVitroDosimetry/	Model	NovaM
In Vivo Particle Delivery	Simulation and analysis of NP-mediated drug delivery via compartmental modeling	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/compsafenano/ivpd/	Model	NovaM
Lung Dose and Biodistribution Tool	Predicts the lung burden and biodistribution of nanomaterials after inhalation in an occupational setting	https://lungexposure.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	Model	NovaM
MouseTox	Online toxicity assessment tool for small molecules	http://enalos.insilicotox.com/MouseTox/	Model	NovaM

MS3bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	Predict the ζ -potential of inorganic engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) in water using molecular, size, and surface-based descriptors.	https://mszeta.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	Model	NovaM
NanoBioAccumulate	Modeling uptake and bioaccumulation of nanomaterials in soil and aquatic invertebrates	https://www.enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/diagonal/pbpk/	Model	NovaM
NanoConstruct	Web-based application for constructing ellipsoidal nanoparticles and calculating atomistic descriptors	https://enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/riskgone/nanocconstruct/	Toolox	NovaM
NanoSolveIT Aerosol Module	Predict concentration of engineered nanomaterials in indoor air	https://aerosol.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	Model	NovaM
NanoSolveIT Facet Cytotoxicity	Predicts metal oxide nanoparticle toxicity based on facet-based electronic, image analysis-based, and periodic table-derived descriptors	https://facetcytotoxicity.cloud.nanosolveit.eu/	Model	NovaM
NanoTube Construct	Digital construction of nanotubes based on single-layer materials and calculation of their atomistic descriptors using Enalos Cloud Platform	https://enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/diagonal/nanotube/	Web tool	NovaM
NanoXtract	Nanomaterials image analysis tool powered by Enalos Cloud Platform	https://enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/NanoXtract/	Web tool	NovaM
PBFTPK	Physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling for analyzing finite-time oral drug absorption and disposition	https://www.enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/PBFTPK/	Model	NovaM
PPAR γ Binding Affinity Prediction	Deep learning model predicting binding affinity to PPAR γ using Tox21 data	https://www.enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/scenarios/ppargamma/	Model	NovaM

	PPAR- γ Cytotoxicity Prediction	Predicting cytotoxicity and binding affinity of small molecules to PPAR- γ	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/scenarios/pargammaliganddl/	Model	NovaM
	PPAR δ Agonist Model	Machine learning model for predicting the biological potency of novel PPAR δ agonists	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/scenarios/pardelta/	Model	NovaM
	Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs	Online toxicity and protein binding prediction for decorated MWCNTs, facilitating the safe-by-design process.	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/CNT/	Model	NovaM
	SafeNanoScope	AI/ML-based in silico assessment model for nanoparticle (NP) toxicity targeting Ag, TiO ₂ , and CuO NPs in terms of safety and sustainability	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/sabydoma/safenanoscope/	Model	NovaM
	THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation	AI/ML-based model to predict chelation outcomes for thalassemia patients	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/chelation/	Model	NovaM
	UANanoDock	Prediction of protein adsorption onto nanoparticles at selected pH levels	UANanoDock on Enalos Cloud	Web tool	NovaM
	Zeta-Predict	Estimation of zeta potential from electron microscopy images	Zeta-Predict on Enalos Cloud Platform	Web tool	NovaM
	Enalos Suite	Package any predictive model in a completely custom made, platform independent, standalone software	https://enalossuite.novamechanics.com/	Platform	NovaM
	Enalos+ KNIME nodes	Enalos+ nodes for KNIME analytics platform which offer a wide range of cheminformatics, bioinformatics and nanoinformatics functionalities into KNIME to enhance the solution of big data analysis, personalized medicine, clinical trials, computer aided drug discovery and material science problems	https://www.knime.com/community/enalos-nodes	Platform	NovaM

eUTOPIA		It is a graphically accessible guided workflow for preprocessing and analysis of omics data	https://github.com/Greco-Lab/eUTOPIA	Workflow	TAU
FunMappone		A tool that allows to visualize and summarize the functional annotations of one or multiple molecular biology experiments at once.	https://github.com/Greco-Lab/FunMappOne	Graphical tool	TAU
GARBO		A novel multi-island adaptive genetic algorithm to simultaneously optimize accuracy and set size in omics-driven biomarker discovery problems.	https://github.com/Greco-Lab/GARBO	Algorithm	TAU
INFORM		A novel computational method to perform inference of gene network from transcriptome data and prioritization of key genes with central functional and topological role in the network	https://github.com/Greco-Lab/INFORM	Application	TAU
INTEGRA		INTEGRA is a unified computational platform that integrates environmental fate, exposure, and internal dose dynamically over time.	http://www.integra.cperi.certh.gr/	Platform	AUTH
Isalos Analytics Platform		Develop and deploy ML/AI models to identify patterns and make predictions without programming (zero code)	http://isalos.novamechanics.com/	Platform	NovaM
Jaqpote Infrastructure		A model repository developed in python and jaqpote making the models accessible through a user interface, that allows extensive documentation of the models and sharing via contacts.	https://jaqpote.org/	Platform	NTUA
Jaqpote Infrastructure	PFAS Half-Lives QSAR	QSAR model that predicts the log ₁₀ Half-Lives of PFAS in mammals.	To be implemented	Model	NTUA
	PFAS Fish Bioconcentration Factor QSAR	QSAR model that predicts the log ₁₀ BCF of PFAS in aquatic organisms	https://app.jaqpote.org/dashboard/models/1976/description	Model	NTUA
	PFAS Root Concentration Factor QSAR	QSAR model that predicts the log ₁₀ RCF of PFAS in plants	https://app.jaqpote.org/dashboard/models/1958/description	Model	NTUA
	PFAS Shoot Concentration Factor QSAR	QSAR model that predicts the log ₁₀ SCF of PFAS in plants	https://app.jaqpote.org/dashboard/models/1975/description	Model	NTUA

QSAR PFAS Albumin Binding	QSAR model that predicts the association constant K_a of different PFAS congeners to Albumin	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1776/description	Model	NTUA
QSAR model for cell viability in Graphene related materials	QSAR-ML model for predicting the lung cell viability percentage based on experimental conditions and material properties of graphene-related materials.	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1881/description	Model	NTUA
PFOA rat PBK (Worley)	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFOA in male rats after intravenous or oral administration	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1726/description	Model	NTUA
PFOA rat PBK	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFOA in rats after oral or iv exposure	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1945/description	Model	NTUA
PFOS rat PBK	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFOS in rats after oral or iv exposure	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1947/description	Model	NTUA
PFHxS rat PBK	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFHxS in rats after oral or iv exposure	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1943/description	Model	NTUA
PFNA rat PBK	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFNA in rats after oral or iv exposure	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1942/description	Model	NTUA
PFDA rat PBK	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFDA in rats after oral or iv exposure	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1941/description	Model	NTUA
Extended PFOA male rat PBK	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFOA in male rats after either intravenous or oral administration	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1730/description	Model	NTUA
PFAS Human PBPK	PBPK model for predicting the biodistribution of PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS, PFDS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA or PFTeDA in humans, who are orally exposed via oral ingestion	https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1691/description	Model	NTUA

	PFAAS Protein-Binding Fish PBK	PBK model for predicting the biodistribution of PFOS, PFOA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDoA, PFHxS in fish, who are exposed via water	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1689/description	Model	NTUA
	PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral Exposure)	PBK model for predicting the biodistribution of PFOS and PFOA in humans who are orally exposed via water consumption	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1687/description	Model	NTUA
	PFOS Rainbow trout PBTK	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOS in Rainbow trout after oral or waterborne exposure	To be implemented	Model	NTUA
	PFOS/PFOA Human PBK	PBK model for predicting the biodistribution of PFOS and PFOA in humans, who are orally exposed via water consumption or via intravenous injections	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1685/description	Model	NTUA
	PFAS PBK Zebrafish	PBK model for predicting the biodistribution of PFOA, PFHpA, PFNA, PFHxS or PFBS in female zebrafish (D.rerio), via waterborne exposure	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1729	Model	NTUA
	TinderMIX	TinderMIX is a computational framework for dose- and time- dependent gene expression analysis which aims to identify groups of genes that show a dynamic dose-response behaviour	https://github.com/grecolab/TinderMIX	Computational framework	TAU
	VOLTA	VOLTA is a Python network analysis package, suited for different types of networks but with a focus on co-expression network analysis	https://github.com/fhative/VOLTA	Python package	TAU

Table 2: Inventory of external tools identified by the INSIGHT partners as relevant for the framework

Tool name	Objective	Location	Type of tool	Developer
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)	ART is a higher tier exposure assessment tool for occupational inhalation exposure to dust, mist and vapour, based on activity-specific exposures.	https://www.advancedreachtool.com/	Model	HSL, BAuA, TNO, IOM, nfa, UU
AMBIT tool	AMBIT is a chemoinformatic tool for hazard predictions, structure similarity, read across	https://github.com/ideaconsult/apps-ambit	Predictive tool	Cefic-Lri
Brightway	Brightway is an open-source framework for life cycle assessment (LCA) and environmental impact assessment	https://docs.brightway.dev/en/latest/content/installation/index.html	Software	Dds
Chesar	Chesar is an integrated tool used for exposure assessment and risk characterizations. It includes three generic exposure assessment models. It can be used for both qualitative and quantitative risk assessment and can provide chemical safety reports (CSRs).	https://chesar.echa.europa.eu/el/download-chesar-3.7	Integrated platform	ECHA
CLiCC	Open-access, online tool for rapid and efficient characterization of chemical life-cycle impacts	https://clicc.ucsb.edu/	Web application	UCSB
ConsExpo	ConsExpo is an exposure assessment tool for consumer exposure to chemicals used in various consumer products. It takes into account inhalation, dermal and oral exposure routes.	https://consexpweb.nl/	Model	RIVM
Consumer Exposure Model (CEM)	CEM is a consumer exposure assessment model that estimates indoor air and dust concentrations, as well as dermal and oral exposure to new and existing chemicals in consumer products and articles.	https://www.epa.gov/tsca-screening-tools/cem-consumer-exposure-model-download-and-install-instructions	Model	US EPA
Danish (Q)SAR Database	The Danish (Q)SAR database provides an inventory of QSAR models for predicting properties of chemicals, including physicochemical and environmental fate properties and (eco)toxicity endpoints.	https://qsar.food.dtu.dk/	Platform	DTU
ECETOC TRA	ECETOC TRA is a tier I exposure assessment model that consists of three exposure models for occupational, consumer and environmental exposure assessment, respectively.	https://www.ecetoc.org/tools/tra-main/	Model	ECETOC

EMKG-Expo-Tool	EMKG-Expo tool is a tier I exposure assessment tool for occupational inhalation exposure to hazardous substances using a control banding approach.	https://www.baua.de/EN/Topics/Chemicals-biological-agents/Hazardous-substances/REACH-assessment-unit/EMKG-Expo-Tool.html	Model	BAuA
EPISuite	EPISuite is a suite that provides QSPR and QSAR models for predicting physicochemical and environmental fate properties of chemicals.	https://www.epa.gov/tsc-screening-tools/epi-suitetm-estimation-program-interface	Platform of QSAR/QSPR models	US EPA
EUSES	EUSES is an environmental risk assessment tool that evaluates all phases of the substance's life cycle throughout its environmental fate. It provides environmental exposure and risk estimates for new and existing chemicals and biocides.	https://echa.europa.eu/el/support/dossier-submission-tools/euses	Model	Developed by EC and RIVM Hosted by ECHA
MERLIN-Expo	MERLIN-Expo is an exposure assessment software that includes a library of multimedia and PBPK models for human and environmental exposure to chemicals	https://merlin-expo.eu/	Software	2FUN and 4FUN projects
MRA Toolbox v.1.0	Integrating various predictive models with related databases on the web platform for computational mixture risk assessment	https://www.mratoolbox.org/prediction/mratoolboxInfo	Toolbox	KRICT
openLCA	An open-source software for modeling life cycle systems and estimating environmental and socioeconomical indicators	https://www.openlca.org/openlca/	Software	GreenDelta
ProScale	A tool for providing a hazard and exposure based scoring to compare chemical risks associated with products in a life cycle perspective	https://www.ivl.se/projekt/proscale/tools.html	Method	IVL
Prospective ERA tool	It is a tool for prospective ecological risk assessment of emerging technologies at product level	https://zenodo.org/records/8113544	Model	RIVM and ULEIDEN
QSAR Toolbox	A software application for predicting and filling data gaps in (eco)toxicity data for chemical hazard assessment	https://qsartoolbox.org/download/	Toolbox	OECD
QSARDB library	It is a library that collect QSAR/QSPR models and datasets	https://qsar.db.org/	Library	QSARDB
RISKOFDERM	RISKOFDERM is a simple-to-use toolkit for the assessment of occupational dermal exposure. It categorizes user-provided information into hazard and exposure data which is used to estimate health risk from dermal exposure.	-	Toolkit	TNO, Eurofins

S2NANO	A portal for the science-based and data-driven approaches to maximize the benefits of nanoscience and nanotechnology while minimizing potential human health issues and environmental pollution related to nanomaterials	http://portal.s2nano.org/	Platform	
SimpleBox4nano	Regulatory relevant multimedia box-type environmental exposure model for nanomaterials	http://sb4n.cloud.nanosolveit.eu	Model	RIVM
SprayExpo	SprayExpo model estimates the occupational inhalation and dermal exposure to aerosols through spray applications of non-volatile biocidal substances.	https://www.baua.de/EN/Topics/Chemicals-biological-agents/Hazardous-substances/Assessment-unit-biocides/Sprayexpo.html	Model	BAuA
Stoffenmanager	Stoffenmanager is a knowledge-based platform that estimates exposure risks to hazardous substances and biological agents in the workplaces.	https://stoffenmanager.com/en/	Model	TNO, Arbo Unie and Beco
USEtox	A multimedia model for human and ecotoxicological impact characterisation	https://usetox.org/	Model	Hosted by DTU
VEGA	VEGA is a freely available software that provides QSAR models for predicting physicochemical and (eco)toxicological properties of chemicals.	https://www.vegahub.eu/portfolio-item/vega-qsar/	Platform of QSAR models	IRFMN
WHO 2017 human variability	Probabilistic data based model to integrate a) uncertainties from BMD (i.e. BMDL/BMDU) with b) uncertainties from animal Point of Departure (PoD) to human extrapolation with c) uncertainties from human variability.	https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241513548 (including link to APROBA excel file containing the data model)	Data and model	WHO & RIVM
ZZS Similarity tool	ZZS similarity tool is a tool for predicting structural similarity of chemicals. It categorizes the substances into similarity with hazard properties (CM, R, PBT/vPvB, and ED properties).	https://rvszoekstysteem.rivm.nl/ZzsSimilarityTool	Predictive tool	RIVM

2.2.1 Tool description

In the following sections, a summary of the tools that were compiled into the inventory is provided, describing their main objectives and functionalities and how they can support the INSIGHT modeling framework.

2.2.1.1 Internal tools

- **AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity (ULEIDEN):** The model developed is suited for the toxicity prediction of organic chemicals for aquatic organisms. It was built using a large dataset of existing toxicity data, which included was used to develop the model. The dataset contains data on a suite of organisms and a suite of chemicals with no data available for most combinations of chemicals and organisms. Also, it is to be noted that there is a lot of variance in the data, even for chemicals and organisms for which for instance OECD test guidelines or other test guidelines have been developed. This sets a threshold for the performance of the model. Nevertheless, the performance of the model is quite good with 68 % of the predictions within one standard deviation, as deduced by comparing predicted and experimental data. Similar performance is obtained for new chemicals (i.e.: ones not included in the test set).
- It is important to realize that no distinction is made between acute and chronic testing as the exposure duration has been standardized to the maximum life span of an organism. This allows to predict toxicity for non-tested combinations of chemicals and biota and these predictions can be used to generate SSDs (Species Sensitivity Distributions) for organic chemicals and for nanomaterials. SSDs are the basis for chemical risk assessment with the 5th percentile of the SSD commonly used as the Predicted No Effect Level. In risk assessment, data limitations commonly hinder derivation of SSDs and the model developed would allow the generation of SSDs for thousands of organisms. A key issue is, however, that validation is needed. Within INSIGHT, the model can be used to compare the 5th-percentiles of chemicals and as the basis for the ranking of the safety of chemicals. Its use is also encouraged when considering substitution of hazardous chemicals. The 'classical' set of toxicity endpoints would not be suited for this purpose.
- **AOP Fingerprint (TAU):** AOP Fingerprint is an R package under development that enables Key Event (KE) and Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) enrichment analysis for gene lists from toxicogenomics data. It maps input genes to relevant KEs and AOPs, producing an "AOP fingerprint" that highlights potential systemic impacts of chemical exposures. Designed to support regulatory decision-making, AOP Fingerprint provides an accessible way to interpret mechanistic pathways, promoting data-driven New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for safer and more efficient chemical assessments.
- **BMDx (TAU):** BMDx is a user-friendly software tool designed for comprehensive Benchmark Dose (BMD) analysis of transcriptomics data. It uses multiple model fits, optimized by the Akaike Information Criterion, to calculate BMD and IC50/EC50 values from gene expression data. BMDx's graphical interface allows easy exploration of dose-response relationships, model details, functional enrichment and BMD comparison across experiments and time points, making it a powerful tool for analyzing dose-dependent gene expression effects in toxicogenomics.
- **Enalos Cloud Platform (NovaM):** The Enalos Cloud Platform is an advanced online and open-source cloud platform for cheminformatics and nanoinformatics. It includes a wide range of predictive models, each equipped with its own graphical user interface (GUI), and offers flexible and powerful cloud computing resources that provide more simple scientific calculations. The platform offers the possibility to reference diverse data sources, which can support computer-aided drug discovery, materials design, and patient stratification decision-making processes.
- **Enalos Suite (NovaM):** The Enalos Suite is a user-friendly and easy-to-use interface that grants access to Chemical Databases, such as PubChem and UniChem. This allows users to retrieve

information for a significant number of compounds with one request. Additionally, its functionalities can be expanded by integrating custom predictive models.

- **Enalos+ KNIME nodes (NovaM):** Enalos+ KNIME nodes offer a wide range of cheminformatics, bioinformatics and nanoinformatics functionalities into KNIME to enhance the solution of big data analysis, personalized medicine, clinical trials, computer aided drug discovery and material science problems.
- **eUTOPIA (TAU):** eUTOPIA is an user-friendly R Shiny application designed to streamline microarray data analysis for omics research. Aimed at users with limited computational expertise, eUTOPIA provides an intuitive, guided workflow that facilitates data preprocessing, analysis, visualization, and interpretation.
- **FunMappone (TAU):** FunMappOne is an interactive R-Shiny tool designed to simplify and enhance the interpretation of functional annotations in omics data, particularly when handling multiple experiments or extensive functional terms. By leveraging hierarchical annotations from databases like Gene Ontology, KEGG, and Reactome, FunMappOne allows users to efficiently visualize, compare, and interpret human and mouse gene functions across experiments in a user-friendly interface.
- **GARBO (TAU):** GARBO is a multi-island adaptive genetic algorithm designed for biomarker discovery in omics data, aiming to improve clinical applications by selecting small, accurate feature sets. GARBO optimises both accuracy and feature set size compared to traditional methods, balancing these through a Pareto-based approach and weighted accuracy-size criteria.
- **INFORM (TAU):** INfORM is an R Shiny application that simplifies the detection and analysis of biologically relevant gene modules from expression data. Designed for ease of use by non-expert users, it combines multiple network inference methods into a single, intuitive interface, allowing users to identify gene networks with high statistical and biological significance.
- **INTEGRA (AUTH):** INTEGRA is a unified computational platform that integrates environmental fate, exposure, and internal dose dynamically in time. In this way, the platform is able to differentiate between biomonitoring data corresponding to steady exposure patterns as opposed to acute, one-off exposures. The INTEGRA modeling framework (Sarigiannis et al., 2016) brings together all available information for assessing the source-to-dose continuum for the entire life cycle of substances covering an extensive chemical space. The major component of INTEGRA is an integrative computational platform that comprises environmental fate, exposure and internal dose dynamically in time using a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) probabilistic analysis framework. The INTEGRA platform includes the following components: a) Multimedia model to account for multi-scale (far field exposure) interactions affecting the environmental transport and fate of chemicals, b) Indoor micro-environmental modeling and detailed personal exposure assessment (near field exposure), c) A generic PBTK model that captures satisfactorily life stage changes and physiological and metabolic efficiency change over an individual's lifetime (from conception till 80 years of age), d) Inverse modeling module for exposure reconstruction and human biomonitoring (HBM) data assimilation.
- **Isalos Analytics Platform (NovaM):** Isalos analytics is a software application for data manipulation and model development especially designed for non-coding experts. It provides the users with the possibility to create and manage data pipelines with easy-to-use functions for data processing, analytics, visualization, and statistical validation. Isalos offers a user-friendly and ready-to-use environment for machine learning applications.
- **Jaqpot Infrastructure (NTUA):** Jaqpot is a computational platform for in silico modeling of chemicals and materials, providing access to its services through both a User Interface (UI) and an Application Programming Interface (API). It is a cloud-ready application that utilizes the strengths of Java, R, and Python, integrating functionalities from various well-established and open-source machine learning and data analysis toolkits. Jaqpot hosts several PBK and QSAR models for chemicals and materials and incorporates renowned QSAR modeling libraries, such as the QSAR Toolbox. The UI offers a user-friendly experience for non-developers to explore its capabilities,

while the API provides developers with the flexibility to integrate Jaqpot modelling and analysis services into third-party applications, Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs), and Jupyter and Colab notebooks.

- **TinderMIX (TAU):** TinderMIX is a novel method designed to improve toxicogenomic analysis by simultaneously modeling time and dose effects on gene expression. Traditional methods typically analyze each time point separately, missing dynamic (time-dependent) dose responses. TinderMIX overcomes this by fitting time- and dose-integrated models to gene expression data, identifying responsive genes through threshold-based maps that reveal dose and time effects.
- **VOLTA (TAU):** VOLTA is a Python package developed to enhance gene co-expression network analysis, commonly used in studying biological systems through network-based approaches. It addresses the limitations of existing tools by offering both full analysis pipelines for beginners and customizable functions for experienced users. VOLTA supports various network types and analysis scenarios, providing multiple algorithm options for each analytical step, such as different community detection or clustering methods. This flexibility allows users to tailor user's analysis according to specific needs.

2.2.1.2 External tools

- **Advanced REACH Tool (ART):** ART is an occupational exposure assessment model that models the inhalation exposure of workers to dust, mist, and vapour, following a source-receptor approach. It is considered a higher-tier exposure model (Tier II), providing a mechanistic model based on activity-specific exposures (Cherrie & Schneider, 1999; Tielemans et al., 2008). The model is divided into near-field and far-field compartments, considering the source of exposure within one (1) metre of the worker's head and the rest of the workspace area, respectively. Finally, it provides the option of applying Bayesian statistics to readjust the exposure measurements. Within INSIGHT, ART can contribute to the model graph by delivering precise estimates of inhalation exposure during worker activities, also addressing the needs of Step 2 of the SSbD framework.
- **AMBIT tool:** AMBIT is a cheminformatic tool, developed by Cefic-LRI that includes several *in-silico* predictive models (i.e., ToxTree) and can provide molecular descriptors and structural alerts (AMBIT, 2018). It is an open-source tool that aims to support companies in the chemical safety assessment process. By using AMBIT, the option of performing read-across and category formation of chemicals is available. Within the AMBIT system, a large database of chemical structures (around 450000), as well as a dataset of 14570 substances from REACH is provided. Within INSIGHT, AMBIT can provide valuable outputs regarding the identification and characterization of chemical hazards.
- **Brightway:** Brightway2 is a widely used open-source life cycle assessment (LCA) software that enables users to analyze the environmental impacts of products and processes. It offers a comprehensive toolkit for conducting life cycle assessments, including database management, impact assessment methods, and uncertainty analysis.
- **Chesar:** Chesar is an integrated tool, developed by ECHA, to support the safety assessment of chemicals (ECHA, 2021). It consists of three exposure models, considering the occupational, environmental and consumer exposure respectively. ECETOC TRA is integrated into the platform to provide occupational and consumer exposure estimates and EUSES fate model to estimate the environmental exposure risks. Moreover, Chesar allows uploading measured data, as well as data estimated by external tools, such as ART, EMKG Expo tool, and others. The platform is connected with the IUCLID database, where it enables the automatic import of information relevant to physicochemical and (eco)toxicological data. Chesar can support the INSIGHT model graph by offering the possibility of an integrated and comprehensive risk assessment tool.

- **CLiCC:** The Chemical Life Cycle Collaborative (CLiCC) tool has been developed by the Network for Characterizing Chemical Life Cycle (NCCLC) initiative of the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) provided funding for. CLiCC is an online, open-access tool for quickly and effectively characterizing the impacts of chemical life cycles. When the exact manufacturing routes and product fates are still unknown, the tool can assess impacts for the life cycle of chemicals and materials early in their development process. Additionally, the it is a platform is applicable to new chemicals, providing and sharingsharingin information on the chemicals' impact during their life cycle.
- **ConsExpo:** ConsExpo is a consumer exposure model, developed by RIVM, that estimates exposure to chemicals included in consumer products (Delmaar & Schuur, 2017). ConsExpo is considered a higher-tier consumer exposure model (Tier II), providing exposure dose metrics. The model covers all three exposure routes, including inhalation, dermal and oral exposure. Moreover, it covers a broad array of consumer products including personal care products, cleaning and household productsproducts, and more. ConsExpo encompasses aspects relevant to exposure scenario and characteristics, patterns of use, etc., while it also provides extensive information, basic exposure scenarios and default values of several exposure parameters.
- **Consumer Exposure Model (CEM):** CEM is an exposure assessment model developed by the US EPA that calculates inhalation, dermal and oral exposure to new and existing chemicals in consumer products and articles. CEM is a lower-tier exposure model that provides screening and conservative exposure estimates covering both acute and chronic doses. It incorporates a wide range of products and articles, as well as a built-in database of default exposure factors and parameters for different exposure scenarios (ICF, 2019).
- **Danish (Q)SAR Database:** The Danish (Q)SAR database, developed by the DTU National Food Institute, is an inventory of QSAR models for searching hazardous chemical properties (physicochemical properties, environmental fate, bioaccumulation, ecotoxicity, metabolism, and toxicity)(DTU Food, 2018). It enables the identification of chemicals of high concern even with no available testing data. In particular, the database includes predictions for 600,000 chemicals and more from over 200 (Q)SAR models. Moreover, the database is linked with the OECD QSAR toolbox. It is a valuable tool that enables the screening and assessment of hazardous substances, contributing to the elimination of animal testing.
- **ECETOC TRA:** The Targeted Risk Assessment (TRA) tool by ECETOC estimates the risk of chemical exposure for workers, consumers, and the environment. TRA tool was introduced in 2004 and is considered a Tier I screening exposure tool. There are three main components of the tool; workers, consumers and the environment. For each component, there is a separate model for exposure estimation. The estimation of worker exposure, inhalation and dermal, is built on a scenario-based source receptor type model and its prediction is based on the scope of REACH Process Categories (PROC). In terms of consumer exposure, the TRA tool includes algorithms for calculating exposure (oral, inhalation, and dermal) for each product. Lastly, the environmental assessment tool of ECETOC TRA is built on the EU Technical Guidance Document (TGD) spreadsheet for estimating environmental exposures (ECETOC, 2012).
- **EMKG-Expo-Tool:** EMKG-Expo-Tool 2.0 approach is an exposure assessment tool that uses a control banding approach based on control of substances hazardous to health (COSHH) Essentials to estimate occupational inhalation exposure to hazardous substances. It is a Tier I assessment tool, easy to use, providing quantitative occupational exposure assessment. EMKG-Expo-Tool estimates exposure to a substance based on its amount used and its volatility/dustiness, as well as on its control strategy(BAuA, 2018).
- **EPISuite:** EPISuite (Estimation Programs Interface) is a Windows-based suite that provides physiochemical property and environmental fate estimations for exposure assessment. It is a screening-level tool that includes several QSAR/QSPR models for the prediction of properties, such as vapor pressure, melting point, partition-coefficient and biodegradability (EPA, 2023).

- **EUSES:** EUSES is software that assists in the quantitative assessment of the environmental risks related to chemical substances. EUSES, as a tier 2 screening model, can be used for performing tier-based risk assessments and integrates the models developed in the EU Technical Guidance Document (TGD). It evaluates the potential hazards of substances to humans and the environment. EUSES examines all phases of the substance's life cycle along with their environmental fate. The exposure assessment is conducted using exposure scenarios and their acceptable worst-case outcomes (ECHA, 2019; Lijzen, 2004).
- **MERLIN-Expo:** The Merlin-Expo-Tool is an exposure assessment software that provides a library of models for human and environmental exposure to chemicals. By using Merlin-Expo, simulations can be performed both deterministically and probabilistically. As part of the software, multimedia, and PBPK models are integrated, and all aspects of exposure assessment are taken into account, from the environment to the internal body tissues. Among its main functions is the ability to analyze uncertainties and sensitivity. More specifically, the Merlin-Expo-Tool includes models for the environment (river, soil), aquatic food (fish, invertebrate, phytoplankton), terrestrial food (fruit tree, leaf, root, tuber, mammals), as well as human exposure (PBPK) models (Merlin-Expo, 2017).
- **MRA Toolbox v.1.0:** MRA Toolbox is a web-based application that implements many calculation methods to promote safe-by-design concepts and assessment of mixtures risk assessment, by evaluating potential combination risks and cocktail effects of chemicals and mixtures. Its main tasks include a) predicting mixture toxicity using four distinct models (CA, IA, GCA, and QSAR-TSP), b) providing risk management strategies, main hazard classifications in MSDS, and regulatory data for chemicals based on KRICT's chemical integrated management system, c) using the PubChem DV's chemical name, CAS number, molecular weight, and molecular structure to search for chemical properties, including external links. Additionally, d) there are two data-saving options accessible for information security. Last but not least, MRA Toolbox aims to promote sustainable chemistry and public health.
- **openLCA:** openLCA is an open-source software tool used for conducting LCA and sustainability analyses of products, services, and processes. It provides a wide range of impact assessment methodologies, making it a flexible and powerful tool for conducting environmental sustainability assessments. Additionally, it provides a comprehensive platform for data management, impact assessment, and reporting for life cycle assessments.
- **ProScale:** ProScale is a method that compares chemical risks associated with products throughout their life cycle using a scoring system based on hazard and exposure. ProScale can cover both human and environmental toxicity and can be applied to any type of product, while it is based on Life Cycle Thinking (Lexén J et al., 2017).
- **Prospective ERA tool:** The prospective Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA) tool is an integrated model that provides predictions of potential environmental risks to soil and freshwater organisms. It integrates future photovoltaic demand and emission scenarios with dynamic environmental fate models to offer comprehensive environmental impact assessments (Blanco et al., 2024).
- **QSAR Toolbox:** The OECD QSAR Toolbox is a software that facilitates the chemical hazard assessment and increases mechanistic and other knowledge about chemical substances cost-effectively. It contributes to the application of assessment, all while protecting human health and the environment. It includes multiple (Q)SAR models used to provide predictions of different properties, including physical-chemical and environmental fate properties, ecotoxicological information, and human health hazards. Furthermore, the toolbox contains 11 inventories of available substances (QSAR Toolbox, 2022).
- **QsarDB:** QsarDB (QSAR Databank) is a library of QSAR/QSPR models and datasets, that its aim is to provide a FAIR repository of models and data. It covers a wide range of endpoints, such as physicochemical properties, toxicity and ecotoxicity. The models are represented in the QsarDB data format. Information of the models can be uploaded from QSAR Model Reporting Format(QMRF) reports.

- **RISKOFDERM:** RISKOFDERM is a toolkit designed to aid in the assessment and management of workplace hazards and chemical exposure. This toolkit offers the possibility of evaluating potential hazards of chemicals regarding dermal exposure or systemic health. The input data is classified into hazard and exposure categories that facilitates a screening estimate of risks arising from dermal exposure. Finally, if the assessment indicates a high hazard, control actions are recommended to mitigate the risk (MILJOE et al., 2003).
- **S2NANO:** S2NANO (Safe and Sustainable Nanotechnology) is a portal dedicated to advancing science-based and data-driven methodologies for improving the advantages of nanoscience and nanotechnology. The focus is to mitigate potential human health and environmental pollution impacts related to nanomaterials.
- **SprayExpo:** SprayExpo is a tool that is used for the exposure assessment (inhalation and dermal) to aerosols through spray application activities of non-volatile biocidal substances in enclosed rooms. It determines the inhalation and dermal exposure by calculating the concentrations of meaningful particle size fractions of aerosols. As part of the model, gravitational settling, turbulent spray mixing, and droplet evaporation are considered (BAuA, 2017).
- **Stoffenmanager:** Stoffenmanager is a tool applied for risk assessment, that provides two types of outcomes, quantitative exposure estimations (inhalation and dermal) and risk bands. The hazard classifications are obtained from the H-phrases by Arnone et al., (2015). The model for inhalation exposure was developed based on a source-receptor model (Cherrie & Schneider, 1999; Marquart et al., 2008) and includes source emission and contaminant dispersion-related modifying variables. In terms of dermal exposure, RISKOFDERM has been taken into account for the model development. Finally, various aspects are taken into account for the exposure estimation, including handling methods, local control measures or inherent characteristics of the product.
- **USEtox:** The USEtox model, which is a Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) model, provides midpoint and endpoint characterization factors for the effects of chemical emissions on human toxicity and freshwater ecotoxicity. The model is applicable to the indoor environment, the urban scale, the continental scale, and the global scale. USEtox's main result is a set of characterization factors for impact assessment. Exposure, fate, and effect parameters for human toxicity and freshwater ecotoxicity are included in the model and are combined to generate the human toxicity and ecotoxicity characterization factors. Human cancer and non-cancer toxicity and freshwater aquatic toxicity are addressed as impact categories in the model (Rosenbaum et al., 2008; Westh et al., 2015).
- **VEGA:** VEGA is a software, developed by IRFMN, that employs QSAR models for predicting chemical properties, such as physicochemical, (eco)toxicological and environmental properties. Some of the QSAR models included in the VEGA platform are the following: EPI Suite, Toxtree, CAESAR, and SARpy. VEGA combines the QSAR models with read-across tools for the evaluation of the results. The QSAR models are based on three essential components: the property being examined, the relevant chemical data and the algorithm that establishes the linkage between them. VEGA provides a specific metric for evaluating the reliability of the predictions, referred to as the applicability domain index (ADI). The ADI value can guide the decision-making and can be used as a first screening step for evaluating the model predictions. In general, an ADI value above 0.85 indicates a good reliability of the model results, where the prediction is within the applicability domain of the model (VEGA HUB, 2016).
- **WHO 2017 uncertainty modelling:** In brief, the approach a) allows a data-based extrapolation from NOAELs to BMDs based on historical animal test data in animals; b) uses as a PoD the probability distribution of the benchmark dose (GM & GSD) for a defined adverse effect (e.g., 5% decrease of lower brain weight) from a critical study; c) uses the probability distribution for interspecies BMD ratios (animal to /animal and animal/ to human) available data from a large set of chemicals; d) uses a probability distribution for human intra-species differences from available data from a large set of chemicals; e) integrates these variabilities by dividing the probability distribution of BMD by the probability distributions for interspecies differences and the probability distribution

for human intraspecies variability; f) finally provides a probability distribution for a human reference dose, for a desired protection level in terms of effect size (e.g. not more than 5% decrease of lower brain weight; the effect for which the BMD was modelled in the animal experiment) and in terms of residual population under risk (e.g. not more than 1% or 0.1% of the human population). The 5th percentile of this distribution would represent a dose that meets the desired protection level with a probability of 95%. Further non-quantifiable uncertainties should be listed, e.g., in a tabular form.

- **ZZS Similarity tool:** This tool was developed by the RIVM with funding provided by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. Based on the molecular and structural similarities of the evaluated substances to known substances that have previously been identified in the Netherlands as “Substances of Very High Concern” (SVHC, or “ZSS” in Dutch), risk assessors, academic institutions, and industrial partners can assess and prioritize (for additional assessment) substances thanks to ZZS Similarity tool (Wassenaar et al., 2022). The RIVM developed it, and the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management provided the funding. The basic concept is that similar properties and effects can be determined by a substance’s high degree of structural similarity (Wassenaar et al., 2022, Johnson and Maggiora, 1990). In order to quickly identify and then regulate new substances of potentially high concern, the similarity tool uses a list of known substances of very high concern as its primary benchmark, aiding in the total workload of assessing new chemicals. The ZZS similarity models generate the substance’s chemical fingerprint to determine a similarity coefficient using simple input such as SMILES-code or CAS number.

2.3 Tool implementation

This section outlines the important characteristics necessary for the implementation of tools within the INSIGHT modeling framework. The implementation of the tools requires the availability or integration of an API, a docker for deploying models, a GUI, and the specification of the type of application or the programming language employed in their development. In terms of implementation, 36 (30 internal and 6 external) of the tools provide an API and 83 (58 internal and 25 external) of them have a GUI available. Moreover, there is a variation in the application type and the programming language of the models. The criteria against which the models are assessed are presented in Table 3 (internal models and tools) and Table 4 (external models and tools) below.

Table 3: Implementation of internal models

Tool		APIs	Docker	GUI	Programming language/application type
AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity		Not yet: GitHub is under development	No	Not yet	-
AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity of metallic nanomaterials		No	No	Not yet	-
AOP Fingerprint		Not yet	No	No	R
BMDx		Not yet	No	Yes	R Shiny/R
Enalos Cloud Platform	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability	Not Yet	No	Yes	Not specified
	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for	Not yet	No	Yes	Python/ML-based web app

Caco-2 cell permeability prediction				
ASCOT	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based / Cloud platform
Biokinetics Model	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based
Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition	Not yet	No	Yes	KNIME Workflow/Web-based
Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs	Yes	No	Yes	Python, Web-based
Ecotox	Yes	No	Yes	Not specified
Enalos InSilicoNano	Not Yet	No	Yes	KNIME, Web-based
Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Not Yet	No	Yes	Web-based
Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool	Not Yet	No	Yes	Web-based
In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	Not Yet	No	Yes	Java, Web-based
In Vivo Particle Delivery	Yes	No	Yes	R / Web-based
Lung Dose and Biodistribution Tool	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based GUI
MouseTox	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based, KNIME integrated
MS3bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based, part of NanoSolveIT Cloud
NanoBioAccumulate	Yes	No	Yes	Java (hosted on Enalos DIAGONAL Cloud Platform)
NanoConstruct	Not Yet	No	Yes	Web-based / GUI
NanoSolveIT Aerosol Module	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based
NanoSolveIT Facet Cytotoxicity	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based
NanoTube Construct	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based
NanoXtract	Yes	No	Yes	Enalos Cloud Platform (web-based)
PBFTPK	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based / Proprietary software
PPAR γ Binding Affinity Prediction	Yes	No	Yes	DeepChem, Keras
PPAR- γ Cytotoxicity Prediction	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based
PPAR δ Agonist Model	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based, Enalos Cloud Platform
Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs	Not Yet	No	Yes	Java, Web-based

	SafeNanoScope	Not yet	No	Yes	Random Forest model on SABYDOMA platform
	THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based
	UANanoDock	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based
	Zeta-Predict	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based, Enalos Cloud Platform
Enalos Suite		No	No	Yes	Java
Enalos+ KNIME nodes		No	No	Yes	Java
eUTOPIA		Not yet	No	Yes	R Shiny
FunMappone		Not yet	No	Yes	R Shiny
GARBO		Not yet	No	No	Python
INFORM		Not yet	No	Yes	R Shiny
INTEGRA	Dietary Exposure model	Under development	Not yet	Yes (PARC SSbD toolbox)	R
	Non-Dietary Exposure model	Under development	Not yet	Yes (PARC SSbD toolbox)	R
	Inhalation Exposure model	Under development	Not yet	Yes (PARC SSbD toolbox)	R
	Multimedia model	Yes	Not yet	Yes (PARC SSbD toolbox)	R
	PBPK model	Not yet	Not yet	Not yet	R
Isalos Analytics Platform		No	No	Yes	Java
Jaqpot Infrastructure	PFAS Half-Lives QSAR	Not Yet	No	Not yet	Python
	PFAS Fish Bioconcentration Factor QSAR	Yes	No	Yes	Python, Web-Based
	PFAS Root Concentration Factor QSAR	Yes	No	Yes	Python, Web-Based
	PFAS Shoot Concentration Factor QSAR	Yes	No	Yes	Python, Web-Based
	QSAR PFAS Albumin Binding	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	QSAR model for cell viability in Graphene	Yes	No	Yes	Python, Web-Based

	related materials				
	PFOA rat PBK (Worley)	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFOA rat PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFOS rat PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFHxS rat PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFNA rat PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFDA rat PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	Extended PFOA male rat PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFAS Human PBPK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFAAS Protein-Binding Fish PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral Exposure)	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFOS Rainbow trout PBTK	Not yet	No	Not yet	R, Web-Based
	PFOS/PFOA Human PBK	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
	PFAS PBK Zebrafish	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based
TinderMIX		Not yet	No	No	R
VOLTA		Not yet	No	No	Python

Table 4: Implementation of external models

Tool	APIs	Docker	GUI	Programming language/ application type
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)	No	No	Yes	Web-based
AMBIT tool	Yes	Yes	Yes	Java
Brightway	Yes	No	Yes	Python
Chesar	No	No	Yes	Stand-alone application
CLiCC	No	No	Yes	Python
ConsExpo	No	No	Yes	Web-based
Consumer Exposure Model (CEM)	No	No	Yes	Access-based
Danish (Q)SAR Database	No	No	Yes	Java
ECETOC TRA	No	No	Yes	Excel VBA
EMKG-Expo-Tool	No	No	Yes	Software
EPISuite	Yes	No	Yes	Windows-based

EUSES	No	No	Yes	Software
MERLIN-Expo	No	No	Yes	Software
MRA Toolbox v.1.0	No	No	Yes	R v.4.0.2
openLCA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Software
ProScale	No	No	Yes	Web-based
Prospective ERA tool	No	No	No	Excel VBA + R
QSAR Toolbox	Yes	Yes	Yes	Stand-alone application
QSARDB library	No	No	Yes	Library
RISKOFLDERM	No	No	Yes	Excel
SimpleBox4nano (Enalos Cloud)	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based
SprayExpo	No	No	Yes	Excel VBA
Stoffenmanager	No	No	Yes	Web-based
USEtox	No	No	Yes	Excel VBA
VEGA	No	No	Yes	Java
ZZS Similarity tool	No	No	Yes	Web-based

2.4 Mapping of modeling requirements

In accordance with the EC SSbD framework and the five-step SSbD assessment approach proposed by the EC JRC, the necessary modeling requirements to support the INSIGHT framework have been addressed and outlined below:

- *Environmental release and fate*: One of the modeling requirements within the INSIGHT framework is the estimation of environmental releases and fate of chemicals and materials. Those kinds of models can provide predictions on the behavior and potential risks of chemicals or materials related to their releases. By estimating the environmental fate and concentrations of a chemical or a material in the different environmental compartments (air, soil, water), it enables the evaluation of its potential impact on the environment, and subsequently on human health.
- *Exposure*: Exposure modeling is another key element of the INSIGHT modeling framework, covering all environmental media (water, air, soil) and addressing all categories of exposure recipients (general population, worker, consumer). The application of exposure models allows for the identification and estimation of potential adverse impacts associated with exposure to various substances. By providing comprehensive toxicological data allows the identification and assessment of potential health and environmental risks related to exposure to a chemical or material.
- *PBPK*: PBPK models offer insights into the internal dose of a chemical within different target organs or tissues, providing a deeper understanding of exposure to various substances. It considers the amount of chemical exposure (external dose) to estimate the chemical amount found within the body (internal dose) over time. The integration of PBPK models with exposure modeling can provide valuable information on the toxicity levels of chemicals and can facilitate risk assessment studies.
- *QSAR*: QSAR models are crucial components within an SSbD assessment and the INSIGHT framework, as they can provide predictions of the potential toxicity of an existing or newly designed chemical that hasn't been synthesized yet. They can facilitate the identification of

harmful substances by providing information on critical hazards, such as carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, reprotoxicity and endocrine disruption.

- **NAMs:** NAMs refer to any methods or approaches applied as alternatives to animal testing, including *in silico*, *in vitro* or *ex vivo* methodologies. In this context, NAMs provide invaluable and robust tools for toxicity and safety assessment respectively, enabling a mechanistic understanding of the chemical and material interaction with biological systems. NAMs are an essential tool for the hazard assessment step of SSbD.
- **Bioinformatics:** Bioinformatic tools are of significant importance in the advancement of exposure assessment, by applying modern toxicity testing methods, such as omics (genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, transcriptomics), to analyze complex biological information and responses to chemical exposure and uncover insights into potential adverse effects.
- **LCA:** A LCA method is used for the evaluation and estimation of environmental impacts throughout the whole life cycle of a chemical, material, process or product, from resource extraction to production, manufacturing, use and end-of-life. LCA is one of the key components of the environmental sustainability assessment part, therefore the inclusion of modelling tools for LCA is of high importance.
- **S-LCA:** Social LCA will be applied for the assessment of potential impacts (negatives and positives) of products or services through their whole life cycle. By implementing S-LCA methods and approaches, the social impacts of a product or service are covered. There are existing methodological frameworks for S-LCA. The three most relevant, which are used as a basis in INSIGHT, are UNEP Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations (UNEP, 2020), Product Social Impact Assessment Handbook (PSIA) (Goedkoop et al., 2020), and the WorldBusiness Council for Sustainable Development(WBCSD, 2018).
- **LCC:** To address the economic impacts of a chemical, material or product, the method of Life Cycle Costing (LCC) will be applied.

Table 5: Coverage of modeling requirements by internal models

Tool		Environmental fate	Exposure	Risk	PBPK	QSAR (Hazard assessment)	Hazard based on NAMs/in vitro	Bioinformatics	LCA	S-LCA	LCC
AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity of metallic nanomaterials						X	X	X			
AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity of organic chemicals						X	X	X			
AOP Fingerprint							X				
BMDx							X				
Enalos Cloud Platform	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability										
	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction										
	ASCOT					X	X				

	Biokinetics Model				X					
	Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition					X				
	Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs			X	X	X		X		X
	Ecotox	X		X						
	Enalos InSilicoNano		X	X		X	X	X		
	Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity					X				
	Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool					X				
	In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	X	X	X			X			
	In Vivo Particle Delivery	X	X					X		
	Lung Dose and Biodistribution Tool		X	X	X					
	MouseTox					X				
	MS3bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	X	X	X		X	X		X	
	NanoBioAccumulate	X	X	X	X					
	NanoConstruct									
	NanoSolveIT Aerosol Module	X	X	X						
	NanoSolveIT Facet Cytotoxicity					X	X			
	NanoTube Construct									
	NanoXtract									
	PBFTPK				X					
	PPAR γ Binding Affinity Prediction									
	PPAR- γ Cytotoxicity Prediction									
	PPAR δ Agonist Model					X				
	Safe-by-design tool for functionalized NMs		X	X		X	X	X		
	SafeNanoScope	X				X	X			
	THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation							X		
	UANanoDock							X		
	Zeta-Predict									
	eUTOPIA							X		

FunMappone							X				
GARBO							X				
INfORM								X			
INTEGRA	Dietary Exposure model		X	X							
	Non-Dietary Exposure model		X	X							
	Inhalation Exposure model		X	X							
	Multimedia model	X	X	X							
	PBPK model		X		X	X					
Jaqpot Infrastructure	PFAS Half-Lives QSAR		X			X					
	PFAS Fish Bioconcentration Factor QSAR	X	X			X					
	PFAS Root Concentration Factor QSAR	X	X			X					
	PFAS Shoot Concentration Factor QSAR	X	X			X					
	QSAR PFAS Albumin Binding		X			X					
	QSAR model for cell viability in Graphene related materials			X		X					
	PFOA rat PBK (Worley)		X		X						
	PFOA rat PBK		X		X						
	PFOS rat PBK		X		X						
	PFHxS rat PBK		X		X						
	PFNA rat PBK		X		X						
	PFDA rat PBK		X		X						
	Extended PFOA male rat PBK		X		X						
	PFAS Human PBPK		X		X						
	PFAAS Protein-Binding Fish PBK		X		X						
	PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral Exposure)		X		X						
	PFOS Rainbow trout PBTk		X		X						
PFOS/PFOA Human PBK		X		X							
PFAS PBK Zebrafish		X		X							
TinderMIX							X				
VOLTA								X			

Table 6: Coverage of modeling requirements by external models

Tool	Environmental fate	Exposure	Risk	PBPK	QSAR (Hazard assessment)	Hazard based on NAMs/in vitro	Bioinformatics	LCA	S-LCA	LCC
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)		X								
AMBIT tool					X	X				
Brightway								X		
Chesar	X	X	X							
CLiCC			X					X		
ConsExpo		X								
Consumer Exposure Model (CEM)		X								
Danish (Q)SAR Database					X					
ECETOC TRA	X	X	X							
EMKG-Expo-Tool		X	X							
EPISuite					X					
EUSES	X	X	X							
MERLIN-Expo	X	X		X						
MRA Toolbox v. 1.0					X					
openLCA								X	X	X
ProScale		X						X		
Prospective ERA tool	X	X	X					X		
QSARDB library					X					
QSAR Toolbox					X	X				
RISKOFDERM		X								
S2NANO										
SimpleBox4nano (Enalos Cloud)	X	X								
SprayExpo		X								
Stoffenmanager		X								
USEtox	X	X						X		
VEGA					X					
ZZS Similarity tool						X				

2.5 Input – output definition

A fundamental aspect of building model pipelines and eventually structuring a model graph is the definition of the inputs and outputs for each model within these pipelines. Therefore, the models and

tools collected within T2.1 were further described with as much detail as possible, specifying their input and output requirements. The following tables (Table 7, Table 8, Table 9, and

Table 10) provide an overview of the types of inputs and outputs in general terms. Specifically, based on the detailed definition of the inputs and outputs of each tool (input/output name, input/output unit, user-defined input or retrieved from database), a more generalized definition of them has been created, serving as a starting point for establishing vocabulary and consequently ontologies for the tools and models integrated into the model graph. Thus, it is imperative to note that this is a gradual process and the generalized types of inputs and outputs provided should not be considered as definitive, but as an initial example of harmonizing the input-output relationships across models/tools.

Table 7: Types of inputs of internal tools

Tool		Input
AI/ML models		Chemical identifier
		Material characteristics
AOP fingerprint		List of genes and associated deregulation values (e.g. fold-change, or PODs)
		KE enrichment parameters
		AOP enrichment parameters
		AOP fingerprint parameters
		AOP network parameters
BMDx		Metadata for omic data
		Preprocessed omic data
		Data format parameters
		Sample identifier mapping
		Dose identifier mapping
		Dose dependent analysis prefiltering parameters
		Dose dependent analysis building model list parameters
		Dose dependent analysis fitting parameters
		Dose dependent analysis computing statistics parameters
		Dose dependent analysis fitted model filtering parameters
eUTOPIA		Time identifier mapping
		Platform-specific variables
		Differential expression analysis
		Normalization
		Batch correction
Enalos Cloud Platform	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability	Choice of annotation
		Chemical identifier
		Physicochemical property
		Prediction statistics
		Visualization

	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction	Chemical identifier
		Physicochemical property
		Prediction statistics
		Visualization
	ASCOT	Chemical identifier
		Physicochemical property
		Descriptors (atomistic, structural, symmetry)
	Biokinetics Model	Temporal parameter
		Kinetic parameter
		Fractional parameter
		Device-specific parameter
		Transfer coefficient ratio
	Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition	Device surface treatment
		Chemical identifier
	Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs	Chemical properties
		Nanomaterial property
	Ecotox	Exposure Data
		Physicochemical property
	Enalos InSilicoNano	Exposure data
		Environmental property
	Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Chemical identifier
		Nanomaterial property
	In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	Particle property
		Chemical identifier
		Physicochemical property
		Environmental fate property
		Exposure Data
In Vivo Particle Delivery	Environmental data	
	Mass	
	Transfer rate	
	Degradation rate	
	Time	
Lung Dose and Biodistribution Tool	Initial dose	
	Time	
	Volume rate	
	Density	
MouseTox	Concentration	
	Chemical structure notation	
MS3bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	Nanomaterial type	
	Coating type	
	Molecular property	

	NanoBioAccumulate	Nanomaterial size
		PBPK parameters
		Concentration
		Nanomaterial type
	NanoConstruct	Time
		Chemical composition
		Shape parameters
		Simulation parameters
		Descriptor
	NanoSolveIT Aerosol Module	Environmental Conditions
		Geometric layout
		Physicochemical property
	NanoSolveIT Facet Cytotoxicity	Emission data
		Scenario descriptor
	NanoTube Construct	Physicochemical property
		Atomic property
		Material selection
		Parameters (force field, structural, replication, machine learning)
	NanoXtract	Atomistic descriptors
		Display settings
		Surface area, thickness
		Nanomaterial type
		Nano-descriptors
	PBFTPK	Statistical filtering parameters
		Image analysis settings
		Pharmacokinetic parameter
	PPAR γ Binding Affinity Prediction	Chemical identifier
		Effect data
	PPAR- γ Cytotoxicity Prediction	Chemical identifier
		Chemical descriptors
Effect data		
PPAR δ Agonist Model	Chemical identifier	
	Chemical descriptors	
	Physicochemical property	
	Activity prediction	
Safe-by-design tool for functionalized NMs	Chemical identifier	
	Physicochemical property	
SafeNanoScope	Chemical name	
	Exposure data	
	Physicochemical property	
THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation	Demographic data	
	Clinical biomarker	
	Health Condition	
	Chemical identifier	
UANanoDock	Physicochemical property	
	Environmental parameters	
	Energy measure	
	Spatial configuration	
	Chemical descriptor	
Zeta-Predict	Physicochemical property	

		Environmental compartment
FunMapOne		Gene id
		Test statistic
		Chemical group
		Input gene list parameter
		Functional annotation parameter
		P-value threshold input
		Display parameter input
		Data selection parameter
		Sample parameter
		Selection parameters (plot, download, clustering)
GARBO		Number of Genetic Algorithm iterations
		Number of chromosomes per niche
		Minimum initial length of chromosomes
		Number of niches
		Path to omics dataset
INFORM		Gene expression matrix
		Differential gene expression matrix
		Options for plot display
		Set of pre-inferred co-expression matrices
INTEGRA	All models	Chemical name
	All models	Chemical identifier
	All models	Physicochemical property
	Multimedia model	Environmental fate property
	All models	Environmental data
	Dietary exposure model, Non-dietary exposure model, Inhalation exposure model	Reference value
	PBPK model	Exposure data
		PBPK parameters
Isalos Analytics		Spreadsheet
Jaqpot infrastructure	PFAS Half-Lives QSAR	Computational descriptors
		Exposure data
	PFAS Fish Bioconcentration Factor QSAR	Computational descriptors
		Exposure data
	PFAS Root Concentration Factor QSAR	Experimental parameters
		Computational descriptors
		Exposure data
	PFAS Shoot Concentration Factor QSAR	Experimental parameters
		Fate property
		Computational descriptors
		Exposure data
		Experimental parameters

	QSAR PFAS Albumin Binding	Fate property
		Experimental parameters
		Conditions of Use
		Computational descriptors
	QSAR model for cell viability in Graphene related materials	Physicochemical properties
		Exposure data
	PFOA rat PBK (Worley)	Physicochemical Properties
		Experimental parameters
		Exposure data
	PFOA rat PBK	Morphometric parameters
		Simulation parameters
		Exposure data
	PFOS rat PBK	Morphometric parameters
		PBPK parameter
		Simulation parameters
		Exposure data
	PFOS rat PBK	Morphometric parameters
		PBPK parameter
		Simulation parameters
		Exposure data
	PFHxS rat PBK	Morphometric parameters
		PBPK parameters
		Simulation parameters
		Exposure data
	PFNA rat PBK	Morphometric parameters
		PBPK parameters
		Simulation parameters
		Exposure data
PFDA rat PBK	Morphometric parameters	
	PBPK parameters	
	Simulation parameters	
	Exposure data	
Extended PFOA male rat PBK	Morphometric parameters	
	Simulation parameters	
	Exposure data	
PFAS Human PBPK	Morphometric parameters	
	Exposure data	
	Simulation parameters	
PFAAS Protein-Binding Fish PBK	Morphometric parameters	
	Exposure data	
	Simulation parameters	
PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral Exposure)	Morphometric parameters	
	Exposure data	
	Simulation parameters	
PFOS Rainbow trout PBTK	Morphometric parameters	
	Simulation parameters	
	Exposure data	
	Morphometric parameters	

	PFOS/PFOA Human PBK	Exposure data
		Simulation parameters
	PFAS PBK Zebrafish	Morphometric parameters
		Exposure data
		Simulation parameters
TinderMix		Gene expression at multiple doses and time points
VOLTA		Genes co-expression networks

Table 8: Types of inputs of external tools

Tool	Input
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)	Chemical identifier
	Condition of use
	Physicochemical property
AMBIT tool	Chemical identifier
Brightway	Life Cycle Inventory
Chesar	Chemical identifier
	Condition of use
	Physicochemical property
	Environmental fate property
	Environmental hazard
CLiCC	Human health hazard
	Physical hazard
	Physicochemical properties
ConsExpo	Chemical identifiers
	Chemical identifier
	Physicochemical property
Consumer Exposure Model (CEM)	Exposure parameters
	Chemical identifier
	Physicochemical property
Danish (Q)SAR Database	Exposure parameters
	Chemical identifier
	Chemical identifier
ECETOC TRA	Physicochemical property
	Environmental fate property
	Condition of use
	Toxicological data
EMKG-Expo-Tool	Chemical identifier
	Condition of use
	Physicochemical property
EPISuite	Chemical identifier
EUSES	Exposure parameters
	Environmental fate property
	Toxicological data
MERLIN-Expo	Exposure parameters

MRA Toolbox v.1.0	Environmental fate property
	Toxicological data
	Mixtures (compounds)
openLCA	Toxicity endpoints
	Doses
ProScale	Life Cycle Inventory
	Condition of use
	Toxicological data
Prospective ERA tool	Mass flow
	Technology demand scenarios
	Substance properties
	Landscape parameters
QSAR Toolbox	Chemical identifier
RISKOFDERM	Condition of use
S2NANO	Physicochemical properties
	Toxicity properties
SimpleBox4nano	Nanomaterial properties
	Nanomaterial-Environment interaction parameters
	Environmental fate property
SprayExpo	Condition of use
Stoffenmanager	Condition of use
	Toxicological data
	Exposure parameters
USEtox	Environmental fate property
	Toxicological data
	Toxicological data
	Physicochemical property
VEGA	Chemical identifier
ZZS Similarity tool	Chemical identifier

Table 9: Types of outputs of internal tools

Tool		Output
AI/ML models		Environmental hazard - aquatic toxicity
AOP fingerprint		AOP fingerprint, enriched key event
		Enriched AOP
BMDx		Point of departure
eUTOPIA		Differentially expressed genes
		Evaluation of technical variation
		Normalization plot
Enalos Cloud Platform	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability	Predicted permeability status
		Prediction confidence
		Prediction class
		Probability metric
	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell	Predicted permeability status
		Prediction confidence
		Prediction class
		Probability metric

	permeability prediction	
	ASCOT	Physicochemical property
		Descriptor (atomistic, structural, symmetry, size)
		Atomistic coordinates
		Simulation data
	Biokinetics Model	Structural configuration
		Internal exposure level
		Excretion level
		Mass of Ni
	Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition	Localized Ni Concentration
		Classification
	Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs	Reliability indication
		Human health hazard
		Prediction reliability
	Ecotox	Nearest neighbors (kNN)
		Environmental hazard
		Structural similarity
		Confidence in prediction
	Enalos InSilicoNano	Toxicity classification
		Biological effect prediction
		Toxicity prediction
		Applicability domain
		Compound ranking
	Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Hazard prediction
		Toxicity prediction
	In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	Prediction reliability
		Environmental exposure estimate
	In Vivo Particle Delivery	Mass distribution
Delivery efficiency		
Temporal distribution		
Lung Dose and Biodistribution Tool	Lung deposition estimate	
	Systemic biodistribution	
	Inhaled dose	
	Regional dose rate	
Mouse Tox	Cytotoxicity prediction	
	Prediction reliability	
MS3bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	Environmental exposure estimate	
	Neighboring ENMs	
	Distance measure	
	Applicability domain (APD)	
NanoBioAccumulate	Environmental exposure estimate	
	PBPK parameters	
	Risk characterization ratio	
	Bioaccumulation	
	Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC)	
NanoConstruct	3D nanoparticle model	
	Descriptor (geometrical, stability, chemical composition)	
	Parameter (coordination, simulation)	
	Indoor exposure estimate	

	NanoSolveIT Aerosol Module	Temporal exposure distribution
	NanoSolveIT Facet Cytotoxicity	Toxicity prediction (toxic/non-toxic)
		Euclidean distance from similar nanoparticles
	NanoTube Construct	Nanotube characteristics (radius, perimeter, surface area)
		Machine learning parameters
	NanoXtract	Structural properties
		Nano-descriptors
		Statistical metrics
	PBFTPK	Particle-level data
		Pharmacokinetic parameter
		Absorption parameter
		Elimination parameter
	PPAR γ Binding Affinity Prediction	Concentration prediction
		Toxicity classification
	PPAR- γ Cytotoxicity Prediction	Toxicity classification
PPAR δ Agonist Model	Toxicity classification	
	Chemical structure comparison	
Safe-by-design tool for functionalized NMs	Toxicity class	
	Binding class	
SafeNanoScope	Toxicity classification	
THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation	Clinical outcome	
UANanoDock	Energy measure	
	Spatial configuration	
	Structural configuration	
Zeta Potential Prediction Tool	Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC)	
Zeta-Predict	Physicochemical property	
	Environmental compartment	
	Environmental descriptor	
	Toxicity classification	
FunMappOne	Functional annotations	
	Chemical clustering	
GARBO	Final population from GA iterations representing biomarker sets	
	Population snapshots saved at each GA iteration	
	Log of evaluation metrics for each GA iteration	
	Weights for final feature ranking	
INFORM	Network analysis	
INTEGRA	Dietary Exposure model	External dose estimate
	Inhalation Exposure model	Risk Characterization Ratio - consumer
		External dose estimate
	Non-dietary Exposure model	Risk Characterization Ratio - consumer
PBPK model	External dose estimate	
		Internal dose estimate

	Multimedia model	Environmental exposure estimate
		Predicted Environmental Exposure (PEC)
		Risk Characterization Ratio - environment
Jaqpot Infrastructure	PFAS Half-Lives QSAR	Kinetic property
	PFAS Fish Bioconcentration Factor QSAR	Kinetic property
	PFAS Root Concentration Factor QSAR	Kinetic property
	PFAS Shoot Concentration Factor QSAR	Kinetic property
	QSAR PFAS Albumin Binding	Kinetic property
	QSAR model for cell viability in Graphene related materials	Health Hazard
	PFOA rat PBK (Worley)	Internal exposure estimate
		Simulation variables
	PFOA rat PBK	Internal exposure estimate
		Morphometric variables
		Simulation variables
	PFOS rat PBK	Internal exposure estimate
		Kinetic property
		Morphometric variables
	PFHxS rat PBK	Simulation variables
		Internal exposure estimate
		Morphometric variables
	PFNA rat PBK	Simulation variables
		Internal exposure estimate
		Morphometric variables
	PFDA rat PBK	Simulation variables
		Internal exposure estimate
		Morphometric variables
Extended PFOA male rat PBK	Simulation variables	
	Internal exposure estimate	
PFAS Human PBPK	Simulation variables	
	Internal exposure estimate	
PFAAS Protein-Binding Fish PBK	Simulation variables	
	Internal exposure estimate	
PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral Exposure)	Simulation variables	
	Internal exposure estimate	
PFOS Rainbow trout PBTK	Simulation variables	
	Morphometric variables	
	Internal exposure estimate	
PFOS/PFOA Human PBK	Simulation variables	
	Internal exposure estimate	
PFAS PBK Zebrafish	Simulation variables	
	Internal exposure estimate	

TinderMix	Dynamic-dose-dependent genes
VOLTA	Co-expression network similarity by edges
	Gene co-expression network similarity by nodes
	Network random walk similarity

Table 10: Types of outputs of external tools

Tool	Output
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)	Occupational exposure estimate
AMBIT tool	Structural similarity
	Physicochemical property
	Environmental hazard
	Human health hazard
	Environmental fate property
Brightway	Environmental impact
Chesar	Environmental releases
	Environmental exposure estimate
	Occupational exposure estimate
	Consumer exposure estimate
	Risk Characterization Ratio - environment
	Risk Characterization Ratio - occupational
CLiCC	Risk Characterization Ratio - consumer
ConsExpo	Environmental impact indicators
Consumer Exposure Model (CEM)	Consumer exposure estimate
Danish (Q)SAR Database	Consumer exposure estimate
	Environmental hazard
	Human health hazard
ECETOC TRA	Physicochemical property
	Environmental exposure estimate
	Occupational exposure estimate
	Consumer exposure estimate
	Risk Characterization Ratio - environment
	Risk Characterization Ratio - occupational
	Risk Characterization Ratio - consumer
EMKG-Expo-Tool	Risk Characterization Ratio - occupational
EPISuite	Environmental fate property
	Physicochemical property
	Environmental hazard
EUSES	Environmental releases
	Environmental exposure estimate

	Risk Characterization Ratio - environment
MERLIN-Expo	Environmental exposure estimate
	Consumer exposure estimate
	Environmental hazard
	Internal exposure estimate
MRA Toolbox v.1.0	Mixture toxicity/risk assessment
openLCA	Environmental impact, social impact
ProScale	Toxicity potential
Prospective ERA tool	Probabilistic environmental risk assessment
QSAR Toolbox	Physicochemical property
	Environmental hazard
	Human health hazard
	Environmental fate property
RISKOFLDERM	Read-across analysis
RISKOFDERM	Occupational exposure estimate
S2NANO	Nanotoxicity prediction
SimpleBox4nano (Enalos Cloud)	Environmental exposure estimate
SprayExpo	External exposure estimate
Stoffenmanager	Occupational exposure estimate
USEtox	Characterization factor- Human toxicity
	Characterization factor - Ecotoxicity
VEGA	Physicochemical property
	Environmental hazard
	Human health hazard
	Environmental fate property
ZZS Similarity tool	Structural similarity

2.6 Impact assessment – SSbD indicators

The INSIGHT framework, by developing an integrated SSbD framework, will cover the four levels of impact of chemicals and materials: health, environmental, social and economic. To capture the impacts covered by the collected tools, a mapping was conducted as described in Table 11 and Table 12. The mapping was derived from the outputs provided by each tool, ensuring a targeted approach to identify the specific impact that it can address.

Table 11: Type of impact of internal models

Tool		Type of impact (Human Health, Environmental, Social, Economic)
AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity of metallic nanomaterials		Environmental
AI/ML based prediction of aquatic toxicity of organic chemicals		Environmental
AOP Fingerprint		Human Health and Environmental
BMDx		Human Health and Environmental
Enalos Cloud Platform	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for	Human Health

blood-brain barrier permeability	
AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction	Human Health
ASCOT	Environmental
Biokinetics Model	Human Health
Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition	Human Health
Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs	Human Health and Environmental
Ecotox	Environmental
Enalos InSilicoNano	Environmental
Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Environmental
Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool	Environmental
In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	Human Health and Environmental
In Vivo Particle Delivery	Human Health
Lung Dose and Biodistribution Tool	Human Health and Environmental
MouseTox	Human Health and Environmental
MS3bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	Environmental
NanoBioAccumulate	Environmental
NanoConstruct	Human Health and Environmental
NanoSolveIT Aerosol Module	Environmental
NanoSolveIT Facet Cytotoxicity	Human Health and Environmental
NanoTube Construct	Human Health and Environmental
NanoXtract	Environmental
PBFTPk	Human Health
PPAR γ Binding Affinity Prediction	Human Health and Environmental
PPAR- γ Cytotoxicity Prediction	Human Health and Environmental
PPAR δ Agonist Model	Human Health and Environmental
Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs	Human Health and Environmental
SafeNanoScope	Human Health and Environmental
THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation	Human Health

	UANanoDock	Human Health and Environmental
	Zeta-Predict	Environmental
eUTOPIA		Human Health and Environmental
FunMappone		Human Health and Environmental
GARBO		Human Health and Environmental
INFORM		Human Health and Environmental
INTEGRA (All)		Human Health and Environmental
Jaqpot Infrastructure	PFAS Half-Lives QSAR	Human Health and Environmental
	PFAS Fish Bioconcentration Factor QSAR	Environmental
	PFAS Root Concentration Factor QSAR	Environmental
	PFAS Shoot Concentration Factor QSAR	Environmental
	QSAR PFAS Albumin Binding	Human Health
	QSAR model for cell viability in Graphene related materials	Human Health
	PFOA rat PBK (Worley)	Human Health
	PFOA rat PBK	Human Health
	PFOS rat PBK	Human Health
	PFHxS rat PBK	Human Health
	PFNA rat PBK	Human Health
	PFDA rat PBK	Human Health
	Extended PFOA male rat PBK	Human Health
	PFAS Human PBPK	Human Health
	PFAAS Protein-Binding Fish PBK	Environmental
	PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral Exposure)	Human Health
	PFOS Rainbow trout PBTK	Environmental
	PFOS/PFOA Human PBK	Human Health
PFAS PBK Zebrafish	Environmental	
TinderMIX		Human Health and Environmental
VOLTA		Human Health and Environmental

Table 12: Type of impact of external models

Tool	Type of impact (Human Health, Environmental, Social, Economic)
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)	Human Health

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union (GA101137742). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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AMBIT tool	Human Health and Environmental
Brightway	Environmental
Chesar	Human Health and Environmental
CLiCC	Environmental
ConsExpo	Human Health
Consumer Exposure Model (CEM)	Human Health
Danish (Q)SAR Database	Human Health and Environmental
ECETOC TRA	Human Health and Environmental
EMKG-Expo-Tool	Human Health
EPISuite	Environmental
EUSES	Human Health and Environmental
MERLIN-Expo	Human Health and Environmental
MRA Toolbox v.1.0	Human Health and Environmental
openLCA	Environmental, Social, Economic
ProScale	Human Health and Environmental
Prospective ERA tool	Environmental
QSARDB library	Human Health and Environmental
QSAR Toolbox	Human Health and Environmental
RISKOFDERM	Human Health
S2NANO	Human Health and Environmental
SimpleBox4nano (EnalosCloud)	Environmental
SprayExpo	Human Health
Stoffenmanager	Human Health
USEtox	Human Health and Environmental
VEGA	Human Health and Environmental
ZZS Similarity tool	Human Health and Environmental

Figure 3: Coverage of the four types of impacts addressed by the tools.

According to the results (Figure 3), all tools, both internal and external, can cover the impacts on either human health or environmental or both of them, while only one of the external tools is equipped to address socioeconomic impacts. This is identified as a gap at the internal modeling level through the analysis of the tool collection, which is of high importance and needs to be addressed by implementing additional tools either within or beyond INSIGHT.

In addition to the mapping between the tools and impacts, a further mapping was carried out focusing on the list of indicators for SSbD, as outlined by JRC. The SSbD indicators cover both the safety and sustainability aspects, indicating the endpoints that need to be defined through an SSbD assessment. The list of indicators guiding the identification of tools are described below (Table 13). They are classified into safety and sustainability indicators, including specific dimensions pertinent to the five steps of the SSbD assessment framework.

Table 13: SSbD indicators

Dimensions		Safety	Dimensions	Sustainability
Human health hazards		Carcinogenicity	Resources and processing- and product-related aspects	Renewable or fossil
		Mutagenicity		Use of critical raw materials
		Reproductive/developmental toxicity		Water consumption
		Endocrine disruption (human health)		Amount of (solid/water) waste
		Respiratory sensitization		Net mass of materials consumed
		Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (including immunotoxicity and neurotoxicity) (STOT - RE)		Reaction efficiency
		Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT - SE)		Atom economy
		Skin sensitization		Material intensity index
		Acute toxicity		E-factor
		Skin corrosion		Circularity
		Skin irritation		Biodegradability
		Serious eye damage/eye irritation		Energy
		Aspiration hazard		Atmospheric emissions
Environmental hazards		Persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic/very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBT/vPvB)	Environmental	Water Emissions
		Persistent, mobile and toxic/very persistent and very mobile (PMT/vPvM)		Climate change
		Hazardous for the ozone layer		Human health toxicity (impact level)
		Chronic environmental toxicity		Ecotoxicity (impact level)
		Endocrine disruption (environment)		Ionizing radiation
	Acute environmental toxicity	Resources: fossil and mineral, land, and water		
Physical hazards		Explosives	Social	Acidification
		Flammable gases, liquids and solids		Eutrophication
		Aerosols		Ozone depletion
		Oxidizing gases, liquids, solids		Photochemical ozone formation
		Gases under pressure		Particulate matter
		Self-reactive		LCA endpoint indicators
		Pyrophoric liquids, solid		Supply chain responsibility
		Self-heating		Customer protection
		In contact with water emits flammable gas		Occupational health and safety
	Organic peroxides	Human rights		

	Corrosivity		Labour rights
	Desensitized explosives		Product cost
Exposure	Occupational exposure estimates	Economic	Profitability
	Consumer exposure estimates		Life cycle cost & externality cost
	Environmental exposure estimates		Market-related criteria
RCR	Occupational exposure: Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) (inhalation, dermal)		
	Environmental exposure: Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) (water, sediment, soil)		
	Consumer Exposure: Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) (inhalation, dermal, ingestion)		

Taking into consideration the endpoints that each model can predict, as detailed in section 2.5, a comprehensive mapping was implemented between the list of indicators and the respective tools. This mapping connects each indicator to a corresponding tool, as it is presented in the figures below: Figure 4 for internal and Figure 5 for external tools, respectively. These figures only incorporate the indicators that are covered by the identified tools, along with the corresponding number for each. The omics based mechanism of action characterization (Omics MoA) is included as an additional indicator for human health and environmental hazards. The indicators for human health are illustrated in blue, environmental hazards in green, and physical hazards in yellow. Exposure and risk indicators are presented in purple and orange, respectively. Sustainability indicators are depicted in red, which covers resources and processing- and product-related aspects, and in grey for environmental dimension. The detailed results of this mapping are presented in Table 16 and Table 17 of Annex A1.

Figure 4: Mapping between the available internal tools and the SSbD indicators. Human health hazards are presented in blue, environmental hazards in green, physical hazards in yellow, exposure indicators in purple, risk indicators in orange, and sustainability indicators in red (resources and processing- and product-related aspects) and grey (environmental).

Occupational exposure estimates, 6	Consumer exposure estimates, 5	Acute environmental toxicity, 4	Reproductive/developmental toxicity, 3	PMT/vPvM, 3	ED (HH), 2	Skin irritation/corrosion, 2	Serious eye damage/eye irritation, 2	Eutrophication, 2	Acidification, 2	
	PBT/vPvB, 4	Human health toxicity (impact level), 4	Carcinogenicity, 3	Ecotoxicity (impact level), 3	Respiratory sensitization, 2	Resources, 2	RCR consumer, 2	RCR env, 2	Photochemical ozone formation, 2	
Environmental exposure estimates, 5	Chronic environmental toxicity, 4	Mutagenicity, 3	Skin sensitization, 3	RCR occupational, 3	Ozone depletion, 2	Ionizing radiation, 2	Particulate matter, 2	Customer protection, 1	Supply chain responsibility, 1	Occupational health and safety, 1
					Acute toxicity, 2	Climate change, 2	LCA endpoint indicators, 2	Human rights, 1	Contribution to local communities, 1	Contribution to societal development, 1
								Labour rights, 1	Life cycle cost & externality cost, 1	

Figure 5: Mapping between the available external tools and the SSbD indicators. Human health hazards are presented in blue, environmental hazards in green, exposure indicators in purple, risk indicators in orange, environmental sustainability indicators in grey (environmental), social sustainability indicators in yellow and economic sustainability indicators in red.

2.7 Definition and discussion of the FAIRness status evaluation

FAIRness status is a significant component not only of the models but also of the datasets in the SSbD arena facilitating the integration of information and ultimately supporting a “safe and sustainable” data driven approach for the development of chemicals and alternatives. FAIR models and data can be integrated in a manner that reduces the uncertainty of calculations and improves the decision-making process from a regulatory standpoint. In the framework of INSIGHT, an initial FAIRness status of the internal models has been assessed. This approach promotes greater efficiency, accuracy, and accountability in chemical development and regulatory assessment, ultimately contributing to safer and more sustainable practices in the industry. For this procedure, an evaluation form has been compiled (Table 14) and completed by the INSIGHT consortium regarding the collected internal tools.

Table 14: FAIRness status evaluation

Findability	
F1.	Are model and associated metadata assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers?
F2.	Are different versions of the software assigned distinct identifiers?
F3.	Is the model metadata publicly available in open access repositories?
F4.	Are the in-model implemented properties well described by ontological vocabularies? Explain.
F5.	Is the model conveniently identifiable through the common search engines (e.g., Google)?
Accessibility	
A1.	Are model and associated (meta)data retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol?
A2.	Is the protocol open, free, and universally implementable?
A3.	Does the protocol allow for an authentication and authorization procedure where necessary?
A4.	Does the model provide an API?
A5.	Is the model reachable through a DOI or other digital identifier?
A6.	Is the metadata of the model publicly available?
Interoperability	
I1.	Can the model exchange information using established standards?
I2.	Does the model utilizes a knowledge representation template?
I3.	Does the model come with a well-established vocabulary?
I4.	Does the model provide functionalities for results conversion in multiple templates?
I5.	Is the model compatible with publicly available data formats (e.g., csv, txt, rds)?
I6.	Does the model provide an API?
Reusability	
R1.	Does the model include licensing terms?
R2.	Does the model include detailed documentation and tutorials?
R3.	Does the model provide support?
R4.	Is the model hosted in a future proof platform?
R5.	Does the model include conversion tools?
R6.	Is the model metadata publicly available in open access repositories?
R7.	Is the model metadata thoroughly described with relevant ontology-based vocabularies ?
R8.	Are model components and its metadata linked with detailed information about their origins?
R9.	Is the model compatible with publicly available data formats (e.g., csv, txt, rds)?

Table 15: Summary results of the FAIRness status evaluation

	F1.	F2.	F3.	F4.	F5.	A1.	A2.	A3.	A4.	A5.	A6.	I1.	I2.	I3.	I4.	I5.	I6.	R1.	R2.	R3.	R4.	R5.	R6.	R7.	R8.	R9.
AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability	Green																									
AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction	Green																									
AI/ML aquatic toxicity prediction model	Green																									
ASCOT	Green																									
Biokinetics	Green																									
BMDx	Green																									
Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition	Green																									
Cytotoxicity (Cell Viability) Prediction for Metal Oxide NPs Ecotox	Green																									
Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Green																									
Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool	Green																									
eUTOPIA	Green																									
FunMappOne	Green																									
GARBO	Green																									
INFORM	Green																									
INTEGRA Multimedia model	Green																									
INTEGRA Dietary exposure model	Green																									
INTEGRA Non-dietary exposure model	Green																									
INTEGRA Inhalation exposure model	Green																									
In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	Green																									
In Vivo Particle Delivery	Green																									
Lung Dose and Biodistribution Tool	Green																									
MouseTox	Green																									
MS3bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model	Green																									
NanoBioAccumulate	Green																									
NanoConstruct	Green																									
NanoSolveIT Aerosol Module	Green																									
NanoSolveIT Facet Cytotoxicity	Green																									
NanoTube Construct	Green																									
NanoXtract	Green																									
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PFAS Fish Bioconcentration Factor QSAR	Green																									
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PFAS Shoot Concentration Factor QSAR	Green																									
PBFTPK	Green																									
PFOA rat PBK (Worley)	Green																									
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PFOS rat PBK	Green																									
PFHxS rat PBK	Green																									
PFNA rat PBK	Green																									
PFDA rat PBK	Green																									
Extended PFOA male rat PBK	Green																									
PFAS Human PBPK	Green																									
PFAAS Protein-Binding Fish PBK	Green																									
PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral Exposure)	Green																									
PFOS Rainbow trout PBTK	Green																									
PFOS/PFOA Human PBK	Green																									
PFAS PBK Zebrafish	Green																									
PPARγ Binding Affinity Prediction	Green																									
PPARγ Cytotoxicity Prediction	Green																									
PPARδ Agonist Model	Green																									
Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells	Green																									
QSAR PFAS Albumin Binding	Green																									
QSAR model for cell viability in Graphene related materials	Green																									
Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs	Green																									
SafeNanoScope	Green																									
SimpleBox	Green																									
THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation	Green																									
TinderMIX	Green																									
UANanoDock	Green																									
VOLTA	Green																									
Zeta-Predict	Green																									

Fully implemented Partly implemented Not addressed yet

The FAIRness status evaluation results of the INSIGHT internal tools are presented in the heatmap above (Table 15). As mentioned before, the primary goal of this evaluation was to obtain an initial overview of the FAIRness level of the INSIGHT inventory of tools. Additionally, the evaluation aimed to understand how easily these tools can be integrated into the INSIGHT methodological pipeline, as well as to identify potential areas for improvement at FAIRification level. The questions described in Table 14 could be answered by three levels of responses, indicating the status of implementation of each criterion: “fully implemented”, “partially addressed”, and “not addressed yet”. An option for additional responses was also provided, along with an opportunity to provide detailed information regarding the status of each question. This evaluation will be updated regularly based on further developments of the models and data (WP3), with the aim of achieving a final FAIRification of models and tools (T2.4). The evaluation results show that there is a variation in the implementation levels across the tool, with some tools already having reached more advanced levels of inquiries (“fully implemented”) than others. Moreover, the results highlight areas where further development and improvement is needed. However, this is an ongoing process, and most of the model providers are directed to providing models/tools with higher FAIRness levels. The detailed results of the evaluation form, including the variety of answers for each tool, can be found in Annex A2.

2.8 Gaps identification

The analysis of the INSIGHT compendium of models and tools and their specifications, has revealed several gaps, which are highlighted in this section. The identified gaps are categorized into three levels-modeling, impact and SSbD indicators-according to the specific modeling needs of INSIGHT framework. These three levels are interconnected, as the availability of models for estimating specific endpoints directly affects the comprehensiveness of impact assessments and, as a result, the coverage of SSbD indicators.

- *Gaps on the modeling level:* The existing compilation of tools has revealed gaps in the coverage of modeling requirements within the internal tools, as presented in Table 5. Specifically, most of the internal tools address the needs of environmental fate, exposure (environmental and consumer), PBPK, and QSAR modeling. In addition, a number of INSIGHT internal tools are bioinformatic tools, while others focus on hazard identification based on NAMs. Regarding exposure modeling, a gap has been identified in the area of occupational exposure modeling. No tools for assessing occupational exposure are included in the current list of internal tools. Consequently, there is a need to integrate tools, mainly retrieved from the identified external tools, that provide estimations of occupational exposure and risk, such as ECETOC TRA and ART. Another identified gap, and thus a modeling need, highlighted by the internal list of tools, is the lack of socioeconomic assessment models. These models are of particular importance for determining social and economic impacts. Additionally, the list of internal tools lacks LCA models, and there is a general scarcity of freely available LCA models for assessing environmental impacts.
- *Gaps on the impact level:* According to the analysis of impacts covered by the internal tools, it is highlighted that only two of the four impact levels are addressed, which are the human health and environmental impacts. This observation leads to the aforementioned gap in models that address and evaluate socioeconomic impacts. As a result, there is a need for the implementation of more quantitative socioeconomic impact models to serve the scope of the INSIGHT framework, while progress in this field will be closely tracked.
- *Gaps on the coverage of SSbD indicators:* The majority of the tool inventory covers SSbD indicators at the safety level, such as human health and environmental hazards, exposure estimates, and risk characterization, while there is a limited number of tools that cover indicators of the sustainability dimensions (resources, environmental, social and economic sustainability). In a more detailed view, the SSbD indicators that are not covered at the internal level are the following: carcinogenicity, endocrine disruption (HH and ENV), reproductive/developmental toxicity, Specific Target Organ Toxicity – Repeated exposure (STOT – RE), skin sensitization, acute toxicity, skin irritation/corrosion, serious eye damage / irritation, aspiration hazard, the hazard to the ozone layer, physical hazards, occupational exposure and risk, environmental impact categories (except for human toxicity and ecotoxicity) and socioeconomic impacts. The coverage of some of the SSbD indicators is based on the data availability of the tested chemicals and materials within the INSIGHT case studies. Specifically for chemicals registered within ECHA, the dimensions of human health, environmental and physical hazards can be covered by data available within the ECHA database (e.g., harmonized or self-classification of CLP, hazards from the Candidate List of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC)). Lastly, the incorporation of additional tools, such as the ones included in the external list, will facilitate addressing of any SSbD indicators that cannot be covered internally.

3 CONCLUSIONS - FUTURE ACTIONS

The INSIGHT compendium of tools and models will serve as a critical point for the development of the INSIGHT model graph, as well as for the implementation of the INSIGHT case studies (VPI). The tools that have been collected during the first year of the project cover a wide range of modelling requirements, such as exposure and QSAR modelling, as well as most of the SSbD indicators described by JRC. Furthermore, both the internal and external tools focus on human health and environmental impacts, while there is one external tool available that addresses impacts at socioeconomic level. As a result, there is a need for implementing assessment models internally that can address socio-economic impacts. Additionally, the integration of LCA models that cover all the relevant environmental impacts into the INSIGHT inventory of tools is of high importance. In this context, future actions have been identified and are described below:

Input-output relationships and harmonization

Input-output relationships will be built based on the detailed descriptions of inputs and outputs that are provided in the current document. These relationships will further establish the model pipelines that will form the INSIGHT model graph. The primary goal is to address all the modelling needs addressed above, and to cover all the levels of impact. Many of the collected tools can provide outputs that can serve as inputs for other tools. For example, QSAR/QSPR predictions for physicochemical properties can be used as inputs for environmental fate and exposure modeling. Another example is the combination of toxicogenomics analysis tools with PBPK models to facilitate dose extrapolation and risk assessment. In alignment with the structuring of model pipelines, focus will be given to the harmonization of inputs and outputs. This is a gradual process that also depends on the selection of tools and models. Therefore, once necessary tools and models for the implementation of the INSIGHT model graph are defined, a more standardized and harmonized description of their inputs and outputs will be provided.

Improvement of FAIRness status towards a FAIRification process

The first FAIRness status evaluation of the INSIGHT internal tools serves as a basis for improving this status as part of their FAIRification process. The results of this evaluation provided an overview of areas for improvement, such as additional actions for enhancing the accessibility and interoperability principles, as well as a view on the tool integration into the INSIGHT framework. Finally, the evaluation form that was previously presented, will be updated according to the corresponding modelling and data developments.

Alignment with the INSIGHT Case Studies

The alignment of the INSIGHT compendium of tools and models with the modelling needs of the INSIGHT case studies is incremental and a high priority action. An activity of identifying the applicability domain of each tool has already been initiated, focusing on the chemicals and materials that will be assessed through the case studies (PFAS, Advanced materials, Antimicrobials). This alignment activity will facilitate the design of computational pipelines that will support the implementation of the case studies.

4 BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abbate, E., Garmendia, A. I., Bracalente, G., Mancini, L., Tosches, D., Rasmussen, K., . . . Sala, S. (2024). *Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials - Methodological Guidance*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC138035>
- AMBIT. (2018). | AMBIT2. Retrieved December 13, 2022 from <https://ambit.sourceforge.net/>
- Arnone, M., Koppisch, D., Smola, T., Gabriel, S., Verbist, K., & Visser, R. (2015). Hazard banding in compliance with the new Globally Harmonised System (GHS) for use in control banding tools. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 73(1), 287-295. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2015.07.014>
- BAuA. (2017). *SprayExpo: modelling exposure during spray applications*. Retrieved March 10, 2023 from <https://www.baua.de/EN/Topics/Work-design/Hazardous-substances/Assessment-unit-biocides/Sprayexpo.html>
- BAuA. (2018). *EMKG-Expo-Tool 2.0: 1st tier IT-tool to estimate inhalation exposure at workplaces*. Retrieved February 19, 2023 from <https://www.baua.de/EN/Topics/Work-design/Hazardous-substances/REACH-assessment-unit/EMKG-Expo-Tool.html>
- Blanco, C. F., Quik, J. T. K., Hof, M., Fuortes, A., Behrens, P., Cucurachi, S., . . . Vijver, M. G. (2024). A prospective ecological risk assessment of high-efficiency III–V/silicon tandem solar cells [10.1039/D3EM00492A]. *Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts*, 26(3), 540-554. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EM00492A>
- Caldeira, C., Farcas, R., Garmendia Aguirre, I., Mancini, L., Tosches, D., Amelio, A., . . . Sala, S. (2022a). Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials - Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://doi.org/https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/487955>
- Caldeira, C., Farcas, R., Moretti, C., Mancini, L., Rauscher, H., Rasmussen, K., . . . Sala, S. (2022b). Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials Review of safety and sustainability dimensions, aspects, methods, indicators, and tools. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2760/879069>
- Cherrie, J. W., & Schneider, T. (1999). Validation of a New Method for Structured Subjective Assessment of Past Concentrations. *The Annals of Occupational Hygiene*, 43(4), 235-245. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annhyg/43.4.235> %J The Annals of Occupational Hygiene
- Delmaar, J. E., & Schuur, A. G. (2017). ConsExpo Web. Consumer exposure models - model documentation : Update for ConsExpo Web 1.0.2. <https://www.rivm.nl/bibliotheek/rapporten/2017-0197.pdf>
- DTU Food. (2018). User Manual for the Danish (Q)SAR Database. Retrieved March 10, 2023, from http://qsardb.food.dtu.dk/DB_user_manual_21_12_2018.pdf
- EC. (2019). Communication from the commission to the European Parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the Committee of the Regions. The European Green Deal. *COM 2019, 640*.
- EC. (2020). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment. *COM/2020/667 final*.
- EC. (2021). COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE

- COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS on Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'. *COM(2021) 400 final*.
- ECETOC. (2012). Technical Report No 114: ECETOC TRA version 3: Background and Rationale for the Improvements. <https://www.ecetoc.org/tools/tra-main/>
- ECHA. (2019). EUSES - European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances. <https://echa.europa.eu/support/dossier-submission-tools/euses>
- ECHA. (2021). Chesar 3 in a nutshell. Retrieved December 16, 2022, from <https://chesar.echa.europa.eu/documents/736332/736362/Chesar+in+a+nutshell.pdf/f9d363f7-c2a8-0260-ca21-829eeb0d3b6d?t=1541414233379>
- EPA. (2023). *EPI Suite™-Estimation Program Interface*. Retrieved February 13, 2023 from <https://www.epa.gov/tsca-screening-tools/epi-suitetm-estimation-program-interface>
- Goedkoop, M. J., de Beer, I. M., Harmens, R., Saling, P., Morris, D., Florea, A., . . . Whatelet, A. (2020). *Product Social Impact Assessment Handbook - 2020*.
- ICF. (2019). *Consumer Exposure Model (CEM) User Guide*. https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2019-06/documents/cem_2.1_user_guide.pdf
- Lexén J, B. E., Loh Lindholm C, Rydberg T, Amann N, Aschford P., Bednarz A, C. P., Dornan P, Downes R, Enrici MH, Glöckner M., Gura E, d. H. Q., Karafilidis C, van Miert E, Saling P, Tiemersma T., & Wathélet A, W. X. (2017). ProScale - A life cycle method to assess toxicological potentials of product systems, Guidance document, version 1.5. <https://www.ivl.se/download/18.556fc7e17c75c8493327e78/1638178602424/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Lijzen, J. P. A. a. R., M.G.J. . (2004). EUSES Background report. https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/6177702/euses_2-1_background_document_en.pdf/51d73868-784b-1476-f201-8a4ba17e78e0
- Marquart, H., Heussen, H., Le Feber, M., Noy, D., Tielemans, E., Schinkel, J., . . . Van Der Schaaf, D. (2008). 'Stoffenmanager', a Web-Based Control Banding Tool Using an Exposure Process Model. *The Annals of Occupational Hygiene*, 52(6), 429-441. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annhyg/men032> %J The Annals of Occupational Hygiene
- Merlin-Expo. (2017). *Merlin-Expo – Exposure Assessment Software*. Retrieved February 22, 2023 from <https://merlin-expo.eu/about/>
- MILJOE, TNO, HSE, HSL, FOBIG, BAU-BG, . . . INSHT. (2003). Risk Assessment for Occupational Dermal Exposure to Chemicals RISKOFDERM
- QSAR Toolbox. (2022). *QSAR Toolbox*. Retrieved December 13, 2022 from <https://qsartoolbox.org/>
- Rosenbaum, R. K., Bachmann, T. M., Gold, L. S., Huijbregts, M. A. J., Jolliet, O., Juraske, R., . . . Hauschild, M. Z. (2008). USEtox—the UNEP-SETAC toxicity model: recommended characterisation factors for human toxicity and freshwater ecotoxicity in life cycle impact assessment. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 13(7), 532-546. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-008-0038-4>
- Sarigiannis, D., Nikiforou, F., Karakoltzidis, A., Agalliadou, A., Rydberg, T., Halling, M., . . . Karakitsios, S. (2024). OS01-12 A computational toolbox supporting the development of Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials. *Toxicology Letters*, 399, S57. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2024.07.161>
- Sarigiannis, D. A., Karakitsios, S. P., Handakas, E., Simou, K., Solomou, E., & Gotti, A. (2016). Integrated exposure and risk characterization of bisphenol-A in Europe. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 98, 134-147. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2016.10.017>

- Tielemans, E., Schneider, T., Goede, H., Tischer, M., Warren, N., Kromhout, H., . . . Cherrie, J. (2008). Conceptual Model for Assessment of Inhalation Exposure: Defining Modifying Factors. *The Annals of Occupational Hygiene*, 52, 577-586. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annhyg/men059>
- UNEP. (2020). *Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020* (C. Benoît Norris, M. Traverso, S. Neugebauer, E. Ekener, T. Schaubroeck, S. Russo Garrido, M. Berger, S. Valdivia, A. Lehmann, M. Finkbeiner, & G. Arcese, Eds.)
- VEGA HUB. (2016). *VEGA interpretation*. <https://www.vegahub.eu/download/vega-interpretation/>
- WBCSD. (2018). Chemical Industry Methodology for Portfolio Sustainability Assessments (PSA). <https://www.wbcd.org/Programs/Circular-Economy/Resources/Chemical-Industry-Methodology-for-Portfolio-Sustainability-Assessments>
- Westh, T. B., Hauschild, M. Z., Birkved, M., Jørgensen, M. S., Rosenbaum, R. K., & Fantke, P. (2015). The USEtox story: a survey of model developer visions and user requirements. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 20(2), 299-310. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-014-0829-8>

ANNEX AI – SSbD indicators

Table 16: Safety indicators

Dimensions	Safety	Internal Tools	External Tools
Human health hazards	Omics based mechanism of action characterization	eUTOPIA, FunMappone, INfORM, BMDx, TinderMIX, VOLTA, AOP Fingerprint	-
	Carcinogenicity	-	VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database, OECD QSAR Toolbox
	Mutagenicity	Jaqpot (AMES end-point), Enalos Cloud (AMES end-point)	VEGA, OECD QSAR toolbox, Danish QSAR Database
	Reproductive/developmental toxicity	-	VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database, OECD QSAR Toolbox
	Endocrine disruption (human health)	-	VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database
	Respiratory sensitization	-	Danish (Q)SAR Database, OECD QSAR Toolbox
	Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (including immunotoxicity and neurotoxicity) (STOT - RE)	-	-
	Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure (STOT - SE)	Jaqpot (DILI, Drug Induced Liver Toxicity), Enalos Cloud (SafeNanoScope, Prediction of MNPs uptake in PaCa2 cells, Ecotox read-across models, Nano Protein Corona model)	-
	Skin sensitization	-	VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database, OECD QSAR Toolbox
	Acute toxicity	-	VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database
	Skin irritation/corrosion	-	VEGA, OECD QSAR toolbox
	Serious eye damage/eye irritation	-	VEGA, OECD QSAR toolbox
	Aspiration hazard	-	-
Environmental hazards	Omics based mechanism of action characterization	eUTOPIA, FunMappone, INfORM, BMDx, TinderMIX, VOLTA, AOP Fingerprint	-
	Persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic/very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBT/vPvB)	T can be modelled for the aquatic compartment using the Aquatic tox model (ULEIDEN)	VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database, OECD QSAR Toolbox, EPISuite
	Persistent, mobile and toxic/very persistent and very mobile (PMT/vPvM)	T can be modelled for the aquatic compartment using the Aquatic tox model (ULEIDEN)	VEGA, OECD QSAR Toolbox, EPISuite
	Hazardous for the ozone layer	-	-

	Chronic environmental toxicity	Aquatic tox model made available within INSIGHT (ULEIDEN)	EPISuite (ECOSAR), VEGA, OECD QSAR Toolbox, Danish QSAR DB
	Endocrine disruption (environment)	-	-
	Acute environmental toxicity	Aquatic tox model made available within INSIGHT (ULEIDEN). Enalos (Ecotox)	EPISuite (ECOSAR), VEGA, OECD QSAR Toolbox, Danish QSAR DB
Physical hazards	Explosives	-	-
	Flammable gases, liquids and solids	-	-
	Aerosols	Enalos Cloud (MultiBox Aerosol)	
	Oxidising gases, liquids, solids	-	-
	Gases under pressure	-	-
	Self-reactive	-	-
	Pyrophoric liquids, solid	-	-
	Self-heating	-	-
	In contact with water emits flammable gas	-	-
	Organic peroxides	-	-
	Corrosivity	-	-
	Desensitised explosives	-	-
Exposure	Occupational exposure estimates	-	ECETOC TRA, ART, Stoffenmanager, SprayExpo, RISKOFDERM, Chesar
	Consumer exposure estimates	INTEGRA	ConsExpo, CEM, MERLIN-Expo, ECETOC TRA, Chesar
	Environmental exposure estimates	INTEGRA, SimpleBox4nano	SimpleBox4nano, EUSES, ECETOC TRA, MERLIN-Expo, Chesar
RCR	Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) for occupational exposure (inhalation, dermal)	-	ECETOC TRA, EMKG-Expo tool, Chesar
	Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) for environmental exposure (freshwater, sediment, marine water, soil)	INTEGRA	EUSES, Chesar
	Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) for consumer exposure (inhalation, dermal, ingestion)	Jaqpot, INTEGRA	EECTOC TRA, Chesar

Table 17: Sustainability indicators

Dimensions	Sustainability	Internal Tools	External Tools
Resources and processing- and product-related aspects	Renewable or fossil	-	-
	Use of critical raw materials	-	-
	Water consumption	-	-
	Amount of (solid/water) waste	-	-
	Net mass of materials consumed	-	-
	Reaction efficiency	-	-

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	Atom economy	-	-
	Material intensity index	-	-
	E-factor	-	-
	Circularity	-	-
	Biodegradability	Jaqpot	-
	Energy		-
Environmental	Atmospheric emissions	Enalos Cloud	-
	Water Emissions	-	-
	Climate change	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Human health toxicity (impact level)	Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs, Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Brightway, USEtox, ProScale, openLCA
	Ecotoxicity (impact level)	NanoXtract, Ecotox, Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs	Brightway, USEtox, openLCA
	Ionizing radiation	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Resources: fossil and mineral, land, and water	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Acidification	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Eutrophication	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Ozone depletion	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Photochemical ozone formation	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Particulate matter	-	Brightway, openLCA
	LCA endpoint indicators	-	Brightway, openLCA
	Social	Supply chain responsibility	-
Customer protection		-	openLCA
Occupational health and safety		-	openLCA
Human rights		-	openLCA
Labour rights		-	openLCA
Contribution to local communities*		-	openLCA
Contribution to societal development*		-	openLCA
Economic	Product cost	-	-
	Profitability	-	-
	Life cycle cost & externality cost	-	openLCA
	Market-related criteria	-	-

ANNEX A2 – FAIRness status evaluation results

The detailed results of the first FAIRness status evaluation of INSIGHT’s internal models are presented below. More specifically, the answers to each inquiry of Table I4, along with the description of the status pertaining to each principle, are included in the following figures. The model providers could address the questions of the evaluation form using three levels of responses, indicating the status of implementation of each criterion: “fully implemented”, “partially addressed”, and “not addressed yet”. An option for additional responses (“Other”) was also provided.

1. Are model and associated metadata assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers?

● Fully implemented	28
● Partly addressed	4
● Not addressed yet	32
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered metadata for the model for this question.

3. Are different versions of the software assigned distinct identifiers?

● Fully implemented	20
● Partly addressed	12
● Not addressed yet	32
● Other	0

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20 respondents (31%) answered release version for this question.

5. Is the model metadata publicly available in open access repositories?

● Fully implemented	27
● Partly addressed	5
● Not addressed yet	32
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered API calls for this question.

7. Are the in-model implemented properties well described by ontological vocabularies? Explain.

● Fully implemented	0
● Partly addressed	9
● Not addressed yet	55
● Other	0

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7 respondents (11%) answered uses for this question.

9. Is the model conveniently identifiable through the common search engines (e.g., Google)?

● Fully implemented	59
● Partly addressed	4
● Not addressed yet	1
● Other	0

62 respondents (97%) answered search for this question.

11. Are model and associated (meta)data retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol?

● Fully implemented	27
● Partly addressed	4
● Not addressed yet	33
● Other	0

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20 respondents (31%) answered https protocol for this question.

13. Is the protocol open, free, and universally implementable?

Fully implemented	26
Partly addressed	6
Not addressed yet	32
Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered HTTPS and JSON for this question.

15. Does the protocol allow for an authentication and authorization procedure where necessary?

Fully implemented	20
Partly addressed	11
Not addressed yet	33
Other	0

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20 respondents (31%) answered JWT authentication for this question.

17. Does the model provide an API?

Fully implemented	32
Partly addressed	6
Not addressed yet	26
Other	0

21 respondents (33%) answered api for this question.

19. Is the model reachable through a DOI or other digital identifier?

Fully implemented	7
Partly addressed	0
Not addressed yet	57
Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered future for this question.

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21. Is the metadata of the model publicly available?

● Fully implemented	27
● Partly addressed	1
● Not addressed yet	36
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered Model metadata for this question.

23. Can the model exchange information using established standards?

● Fully implemented	20
● Partly addressed	7
● Not addressed yet	37
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered https protocol for this question.

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25. Does the model utilizes a knowledge representation template?

● Fully implemented	1
● Partly addressed	0
● Not addressed yet	63
● Other	0

3 respondents (5%) answered structured for this question.

27. Does the model come with a well-established vocabulary?

● Fully implemented	2
● Partly addressed	38
● Not addressed yet	24
● Other	0

30 respondents (47%) answered ontologies for this question.

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29. Does the model provide functionalities for results conversion in multiple templates?

Fully implemented	0
Partly addressed	27
Not addressed yet	37
Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered representation format for this question.

31. Is the model compatible with publicly available data formats (e.g., csv, txt, rds)?

Fully implemented	35
Partly addressed	27
Not addressed yet	2
Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered csv or json for this question.

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33. Does the model include licensing terms?

● Fully implemented	7
● Partly addressed	4
● Not addressed yet	53
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered licensing terms for this question.

35. Does the model include detailed documentation and tutorials?

● Fully implemented	54
● Partly addressed	7
● Not addressed yet	3
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered model description for this question.

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37. Does the model provide support?

● Fully implemented	52
● Partly addressed	12
● Not addressed yet	0
● Other	0

51 respondents (80%) answered users for this question.

39. Is the model hosted in a future proof platform?

● Fully implemented	58
● Partly addressed	4
● Not addressed yet	2
● Other	0

31 respondents (48%) answered Cloud Platform for this question.

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41. Does the model include conversion tools?

● Fully implemented	20
● Partly addressed	3
● Not addressed yet	41
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered ONNX for this question.

43. Is the model metadata publicly available in open access repositories?

● Fully implemented	28
● Partly addressed	1
● Not addressed yet	35
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered API using HTTPS for this question.

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45. Are model components and its metadata linked with detailed information about their origins?

● Fully implemented	28
● Partly addressed	5
● Not addressed yet	31
● Other	0

20 respondents (31%) answered user account for this question.

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